

Implementing a System for the Computation of
Syntax Splittings for Total Preorders and for
Conditional Knowledge Bases

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Master's Thesis

**Implementing a System for the Computation of
Syntax Splittings for Total Preorders and for
Conditional Knowledge Bases**

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Abstract

In the context of knowledge representation and reasoning, the consideration of relevance plays a major role. The concept of syntax splitting has received an increasing amount of attention in recent years and has been investigated together with other contemporary methods. Originally formulated with respect to belief revision of belief sets, in 2017 Kern-Isberner and Brewka introduced the notion of syntax splitting for total preorders, and in 2020 Kern-Isberner *et al.* provided a basic notion of syntax splitting of conditional knowledge bases within the setting of non-monotonic reasoning. The work presented in this thesis extends the Java library `InfOCF-Lib` by the possibility to read and represent total preorders and to compute syntax splittings of epistemic states represented by total preorders as well as the unique finest syntax splitting of conditional knowledge bases in an automated way. For this purpose, the concept of splittability is introduced, which enables the calculation of syntax splittings for total preorders to be modelled and solved as a modified subset-sum problem. Moreover, with Makinson's notion of epistemic relevance, it is possible to calculate syntax splittings for conditional knowledge bases by considering the conditionals as epistemic knowledge that must not be split. This connection can be recognised and calculated by the transitive closure of the atoms in the conditionals. Based on these concepts, suitable algorithms are developed, implemented in `InfOCF-Lib`, and then evaluated whether concurrent processing brings a runtime advantage. To calculate syntax splittings for ranking functions, a basic approach is provided to model and solve this as a subset-sum problem as well.

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Introduction

” *Intelligence consists in ignoring things that are irrelevant.*

— **Nassim Nicholas Taleb [Tal10]**
(Lebanese-American Mathematical Statistician)

Separating different kinds of knowledge is a natural characteristic in the research field of knowledge representation and reasoning, as for instance, a “simple” knowledge-based system will always differentiate between background and evidential knowledge or between its knowledge base and its inference component. Thorough distinction of relevant and irrelevant knowledge generated considerable research interest that goes far back in history. Traces of definitions aimed at capturing relevance in propositional logic can even be found in the mid-19th century [Mak07], defining syntactical relevance between two formulae as the sharing of elementary letters (atoms, variables), so that the absence of common letters in both formulae can be seen as a prerequisite for capturing irrelevance.

The consideration of relevance in artificial intelligence is still a highly topical issue. For instance, the properties mentioned in [Wei99; WJ95; Woo02] that agents should have, namely reactivity, proactivity and social competence, require the incorporation of only relevant knowledge. To give a clearer picture, Wu *et al.* [WJZ16] have mentioned the increasing significance of providing only relevant parts of knowledge, since robots with limited resources need to exchange data with a cloud system on the one hand and with other robots in their local vicinity on the other. So it is rather useful if the data to be exchanged consists of only relevant knowledge.

With extensive studies in the field of belief change, originating from the seminal AGM theory [AGM85], named after its founders Alchourrón, Gärdenfors and Makinson, two concepts in identifying syntactical relevance have been established. Rodrigues defined the notion of *path-relevance* [Rod98] in 1997, where he stated that two atoms are relevant to each other if and only if there is a finite sequence of formulae between the two atoms such that one can “reach” the other through transitive closure. However, path-relevance came with a certain syntax-dependency in the context of belief sets, which could be remedied by Parikh’s concept of the splitting of a *theory*

\mathcal{T} [Par99], where Parikh provided a notion of relevance through *cell-relevance* of partitioned formulae. With his axiom (P), Parikh claimed that a theory \mathcal{T} can be represented using *syntax splitting* as being composed of mutually independent parts.

Makinson generalised those two approaches, proving equivalence between path-relevance and cell-relevance and thus calling his concept of relevance just *canonical relevance* which is fully syntax-independent [Mak07]. Makinson generalised these relevance considerations even further to the level of firstly *parametrised relevance*, where not only a set of formulae K is being considered, but also a relation R over letters. The second generalisation considered a set of formulae K plus a subset $K' \subseteq K$ which provides syntax independence except in K' . He called that *epistemic relevance* with K' providing epistemic knowledge.

More recently the challenging area of relevance again attracted growing interest, when Peppas *et al.* investigated Parikh's notion of syntax splitting and discovered that his axiom (P) could be read in two different ways: “weak (P)” and “strong (P)” [Pep+15], where “weak (P)” meant that the irrelevant part cannot be affected by belief change, and “strong (P)” stated that, additionally to the irrelevant part not being affected, the change of the relevant part does not depend on the irrelevant part. Those two readings provided restrictions for revision operators, “weak (P)” allowing context dependencies while “strong (P)” did not.

Generalizing the approaches of Parikh and Peppas *et al.*, Kern-Isberner and Brewka lifted their axioms to the level of epistemic states represented by total preorders on worlds in general and in the specific framework of ranking functions, thus making way for implementations of syntax splitting for computational attempts [KIB17]. By identifying marginalisation (well-known from probalistics, where the marginal probability is the probability of a single event occurring, independent of other events) as the basic concept to be used for syntax splitting in the context of epistemic states, they were able to define marginalisation and strong syntax splitting for epistemic states.

As mentioned in [KIB17], their techniques of syntax splitting in the context of belief revision can easily be broadened to the level of (plausible) *conditionals* ($B|A$) [KI01], *i.e.*, defeasible rules of the form “if A , then plausibly (usually, typically, etc.) B ” which has been done recently in [HBKI21b].

In [KIBB20], Kern-Isberner *et al.* addressed syntax splitting in the context of *non-monotonic reasoning* from *conditional knowledge bases*, *i.e.*, sets of conditionals, and therefore introduced syntax splitting for conditional knowledge bases. They defined

postulates (Rel) and (Ind), making way for using techniques of syntax splitting to reason in a much more efficient way concerning non-monotonic inference. In their work, a basic definition of binary syntax splittings of conditional knowledge bases was given.

Besides syntax splitting, another topic has been researched recently, namely *semantic splitting*, where Beierle *et al.* show that in certain cases every syntax splitting of a conditional knowledge base is a semantic splitting as well [BHK12].

Although many contributions have been made in the area of syntax splitting, few researchers have addressed the problem of developing and implementing methods to actually compute syntax splittings. There is one considerable approach of Wu and Zhang in [WZ10] for the computation of the unique finest \mathcal{T} -splitting in polynomial time. Unfortunately, as pointed out by Kern-Isberner and Brewka [KIB17], syntax splitting of belief sets cannot capture iterated belief revision, which was the main motivation for them studying syntax splitting for epistemic states. Their provision of epistemic syntax splitting inspired the present work to develop and implement algorithms to calculate all syntax splittings for a given total preorder.

Besides the above mentioned algorithm to calculate the unique finest \mathcal{T} -splitting for the framework of belief sets and the considerations regarding syntax splittings for the framework of epistemic states represented by total preorders, there is another “missing” algorithm, as Figure 1.1 indicates.

Fig. 1.1.: Connection between knowledge base, epistemic state and belief set

Considering an arbitrary knowledge base, one can model an epistemic state through inductive inference, containing all the information an agent needs for her reasoning. Coming from this epistemic state, a belief set, *i.e.*, the formulae the agent considers to be true, or the *most plausible* knowledge, can be achieved through projection, where only a subset of the epistemic state is being considered.

As mentioned earlier, besides the missing algorithm for calculating syntax splittings for total preorders, there is also no algorithm for calculating syntax splittings for knowledge bases, whose formulation is also covered in this thesis. But before the implementation of any algorithm, there has to be a theoretical fundament for an algorithm to be based on, which will also be provided by this work.

To summarise the main contributions of this thesis:

- a formal definition of the unique finest syntax splitting for conditional knowledge bases,
- algorithms to calculate all syntax splittings for any given total preorder,
- algorithms to calculate the unique finest syntax splitting of any conditional knowledge base,
- the augmentation of `InfOCF-Lib`¹ [Kut19] with total preorders,
- the implementation of said algorithms into `InfOCF-Lib`.

The rest of this thesis will be organised as follows: Formal preliminaries are given in Chapter 2. Chapter 3 introduces syntax splitting in the three different frameworks, *i.e.*, belief sets, epistemic states represented by total preorders on worlds and conditional knowledge bases. Algorithms which are able to calculate all syntax splittings for total preorders and the unique finest syntax splitting for any given conditional knowledge base will be presented in Chapter 4. Chapter 5 discusses the technical implementation of the developed algorithms into the system `InfOCF-Lib`. This implementation is then evaluated in Chapter 6. Challenges with the stated problems as well as examples for possible further extensions of `InfOCF-Lib` will be given in Chapter 7. Chapter 8 concludes this thesis with a short revisit of the preceding chapters.

¹www.fernuni-hagen.de/wbs/data/InfOCF-Lib.zip

Formal Preliminaries

Knowledge can be represented in many different ways, but a common way of representing knowledge bases is in the form of dependent sentences “if A , then B ”, which can be formalised in rule-based systems as *material implications* $A \Rightarrow B$. The field of knowledge representation and reasoning is not only concerned with the representation of knowledge, but also, as the name suggests, with reasoning, the art of deducing facts from facts.

Peirce has shown that in addition to deductive reasoning, inference can also be of inductive or abductive character [HPW31]. Although inference on knowledge bases is not the main concern here, the entities that can be achieved through inductive reasoning, what they look like and how syntax splitting can be applied on those entities will be considered.

There are various ways to represent uncertainty with common logical systems. This thesis deals with the extension of classical logic by *preferential semantics* on the semantic side and by conditionals on the syntactic side, and in particular how syntax splitting can be performed algorithmically on these extensions.

For this purpose, the following sections describe the notation used here for propositional logic, accompanied by these syntactical and semantical extensions.

2.1 Propositional Logic

The notation will be as follows and will largely follow [KIBB20]:

Propositional logic is defined by two components, a syntax and a semantics. Let \mathcal{L}_Σ be a finitely generated propositional language with its syntax consisting of a *signature* Σ with atoms a, b, c, \dots and the set of all propositional formulae over Σ , A, B, C, \dots with the logical connectors \wedge (*and*), \vee (*or*) and \neg (*negation*). To simplify notation, $A \wedge B$ is written AB and the bar above formulae indicates negation, *i.e.*, \bar{A} means $\neg A$. The symbol \top denotes tautologies, \perp stands for contradictions.

Over a given signature Σ , the formulae must be interpreted semantically. The various interpretations can be taken as *possible worlds* $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$ and, with slight

disregard for notation, can also be called *complete conjunctions*, since every possible conjunctive combination is shown by them, which allows the use of ω both as an interpretation and as a proposition; $\Omega(\Sigma)$, also called the *universe* is taken as the set of all propositional interpretations over Σ .

The relation $\omega \models A$ means that the propositional formula $A \in \mathcal{L}_\Sigma$ holds in the possible world $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$; in this case ω is called a *model* of A , and the set of all models of A is denoted by $\text{Mod}_\Sigma(A)$. A formula with at least one model is called *consistent*, otherwise *inconsistent*. For formulae $A, B \in \mathcal{L}_\Sigma$, A entails B if all models of A are contained in the models of B , i.e., $A \models B$ if $\text{Mod}_\Sigma(A) \subseteq \text{Mod}_\Sigma(B)$.

Example 2.1. Let $\Sigma_{abc} = \{a, b, c\}$ be a signature. Then $\Omega(\Sigma)$ is $\{abc, abc\bar{c}, \bar{a}bc, \bar{a}b\bar{c}, \bar{a}\bar{b}c, \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}, \bar{a}bc\bar{c}, \bar{a}\bar{b}c\bar{c}\}$ and $\text{Mod}_{abc}(a) = \{abc, abc\bar{c}, \bar{a}bc, \bar{a}bc\bar{c}\}$.

These concepts of models, consistency, and inference are used correspondingly for sets of formulae. For $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_\Sigma$, the *deductive closure* of \mathcal{G} is $\text{Cn}_\Sigma(\mathcal{G}) = \{A \in \mathcal{L}_\Sigma \mid \mathcal{G} \models A\}$. A *theory* \mathcal{T} of \mathcal{L}_Σ is any set of formulae $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_\Sigma$ of \mathcal{L}_Σ *deductively closed* under \models . The theory of a set $\Omega'(\Sigma) \subseteq \Omega(\Sigma)$ is $\mathcal{T}(\Omega'(\Sigma)) = \{A \in \mathcal{L}_\Sigma \mid \text{for all } \omega \in \Omega'(\Sigma) : \omega \models A\}$. For any theory, $\mathcal{T} = \text{Cn}_\Sigma(\mathcal{T})$. Note that the result of the Cn operator depends entirely on the logical language used.

Example 2.2. Let $\Sigma_{abc} = \{a, b, c\}$ be a signature, and let $\mathcal{T} = \text{Cn}(\{a \wedge (b \vee \bar{b}) \wedge \bar{c}\})$ be a theory. \mathcal{T} is equal to $\text{Cn}(\{a \wedge \bar{c}\})$ and \mathcal{T} is even equal to $\text{Cn}(\{a, \bar{c}\})$.

For subsets $\Theta \subseteq \Sigma$, let \mathcal{L}_Θ denote the propositional language defined by Θ with the associated set of interpretations $\Omega(\Theta)$. Note that while any set of \mathcal{L}_Θ can also be regarded as a set of \mathcal{L}_Σ , the interpretations $\omega^\Theta \in \Omega(\Theta)$ are not elements of $\Omega(\Sigma)$ if $\Theta \neq \Sigma$. But any interpretation $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$ can be uniquely written in the form $\omega = \omega^\Theta \omega^{\bar{\Theta}}$ with concatenated $\omega^\Theta \in \Omega(\Theta)$ and $\omega^{\bar{\Theta}} \in \Omega(\bar{\Theta})$, where $\bar{\Theta} = \Sigma \setminus \Theta$ is the complement of Θ in Σ . Note that the syntactic reading of interpretations as conjunctions makes perfect sense here: according to this reading, ω is a conjunction of ω^Θ and $\omega^{\bar{\Theta}}$ (with \wedge symbol omitted). According to [Del17] ω^Θ is called the *reduct* of ω to Θ . If $\Omega' \subseteq \Omega$ is a subset of models, then $\Omega'|_\Theta = \{\omega^\Theta \mid \omega \in \Omega'\} \subseteq \Omega(\Theta)$ restricts Ω' to a subset of $\Omega(\Theta)$. Considering below the case, where $\{\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_n\}$ are disjoint sub-signatures of Σ , the reductions are denoted ω^i instead of ω^{Σ_i} to simplify notation.

For $A \in \mathcal{L}_\Sigma$ the set $\Sigma(A) \subseteq \Sigma$ denotes the smallest set of variables that is necessary to represent a formula that is equivalent to A . Note that tautologies \top are part of any sub-language \mathcal{L}_Θ of \mathcal{L}_Σ .

2.2 Knowledge Bases and Belief Sets

A *knowledge base* is a subset $KB \subseteq \mathcal{L}_\Sigma$ of the underlying language, or more precisely a subset of the set of formulae that can be constructed from the propositional (finite) signature Σ . Every intelligent agent has a knowledge base with formulae representing her explicit knowledge, but she does not necessarily believe all of those formulae to be true, as the implications of those formulae (*i.e.*, her implicit knowledge, which can be achieved through deductive, inductive, or abductive reasoning [HPW31]) might result in a contradiction. Nonetheless the knowledge base is a crucial part as it provides the foundation on which the agent builds her beliefs. The set of formulae considered to be true by the agent is called *belief set* [Han99; FH11]. In general, agents consider the implications of their belief set \mathcal{T} also to be true, *i.e.*, \mathcal{T} is a deductively closed set $\mathcal{T} = \text{Cn}(\mathcal{T})$.

There will be at least one of the possible worlds over the language the agent “speaks” in which the formulae of the belief set are true. As new information emerges, the agent might be compelled to change her beliefs, as previously accepted beliefs can become incompatible with the new evidence.

Alchourrón, Gärdenfors, and Makinson defined postulates for belief sets and their expansion, contraction, or revision with new evidence [AGM85]. Belief set expansion is the process of incorporating a new piece of evidence that is consistent with currently held beliefs. Contraction refers to giving up a belief that has become questionable. The process of belief revision refers to keeping an agent’s set of beliefs consistent, while incorporating new information that can be inconsistent with the current belief set [KM91].

However, belief sets are unsuitable for computational implementation as they are cardinally infinite. There is even another problem with belief sets in the context of belief change, as it does not cover iterated belief change, *i.e.*, the repetitive application of belief change operators. The outcome of iterated belief change applied on belief sets can result in unjustifiable abandonment of knowledge [DP97].

2.3 Epistemic States and Total Preorders

In their seminal work, Darwiche and Pearl proposed *epistemic states* [DP97], *i.e.*, abstract entities that contain all the information an agent needs when drawing her inferences. This includes not only her belief set but also implicit beliefs, *i.e.*, conditional knowledge that the agent is willing to believe.

To represent these epistemic states, *preferential models* [Mak88] were used. Based on Makinson's preferential semantics², preferential models are semantic structures capable of associating the relation \models with non-logical information such as normality, plausibility, etc.

The epistemic states considered in this thesis are hereby characterised only by a plausibility order of propositional interpretations or possible worlds such that one world is more plausible or more preferred than another if it is *smaller* concerning the order which expresses the plausibility.

Frequently used preferential relations are *total preorders* (TPOs) \preceq on possible worlds. TPOs are binary relations \preceq (in this context over the set of propositional worlds $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$) that are total, reflexive, and transitive, *i.e.*, for all $\omega, \omega', \omega'' \in \Omega(\Sigma)$: either $\omega \preceq \omega'$ or $\omega' \preceq \omega$, $\omega \preceq \omega$, and if $\omega \preceq \omega'$ and $\omega' \preceq \omega''$, then $\omega \preceq \omega''$. The symbol \prec is used to denote the strict part of \preceq while \sim represents the symmetric closure of \preceq (*i.e.*, $\omega \prec \omega'$ *iff* $\omega \preceq \omega'$ and $\omega' \not\preceq \omega$; and $\omega \sim \omega'$ *iff* $\omega \preceq \omega'$ and $\omega' \preceq \omega$). For conciseness of notation the symmetric closure \sim when used to represent TPOs, will be abbreviated in this thesis, representing a TPO by an ordered set of layers, where

$$\begin{array}{ccc} ab & & \bar{a}\bar{b} \\ \bar{a}b & \prec & \bar{a}\bar{b} \end{array}$$

means that the worlds ab and $\bar{a}b$ are contained in one layer while the worlds $\bar{a}\bar{b}$ and $\bar{a}b$ are also contained in one layer, or just in one line, *i.e.*, $ab, \bar{a}b \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}, \bar{a}b$.

Example 2.3. Let $\Sigma_{abc} = \{a, b, c\}$ be a signature, and let Ψ_{abc} be an epistemic state with a TPO $\preceq_{\Psi_{abc}}$ defined on Σ_{abc} : $\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec ab\bar{c} \prec \bar{a}bc \prec abc, \bar{a}\bar{b}c, \bar{a}b\bar{c} \prec \bar{a}bc, \bar{a}bc$.

In this epistemic state, the world $\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$ in the leftmost layer represents the most preferred world under the TPO $\preceq_{\Psi_{abc}}$, while $\bar{a}bc$ and $\bar{a}b\bar{c}$ in the rightmost layer represent the least preferred worlds under the TPO $\preceq_{\Psi_{abc}}$.

TPOs on the set of interpretations can be lifted to TPOs on the set of propositions (formulae) via $A \preceq B$ *iff* there is an $\omega \in \text{Mod}(A)$ such that $\omega \preceq \omega'$ for all $\omega' \in \text{Mod}(B)$.

Belief sets can be excerpted from epistemic states Ψ , which is denoted as $\text{Bel}(\Psi)$. Extraction of the belief set is achieved by considering the set of lowest ranked worlds (*i.e.*, the most plausible interpretations) under \preceq_{Ψ} . The set of propositional sentences that holds in all those worlds is defined to be the belief set of the agent, *i.e.*,

²Kraus, Lehmann, and Magidor have proposed a similar notion of a plausibility ranking [KLM90].

$\text{Bel}(\Psi) = \mathcal{T}(\min(\Psi))$. These sets are called *minimal models*. It is straightforward to see that in Example 2.3 above the world $\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$ depicts the most plausible world and as such, all formulae that hold in $\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$ are contained in the belief set. Similarly, for subsets of Ω : if $\Omega' \subseteq \Omega$, then $\min(\Psi, \Omega') = \min(\preceq_\Psi, \Omega') = \{\omega' \in \Omega' \mid \omega' \preceq_\Psi \omega'' \text{ for all } \omega'' \in \Omega'\}$ denotes the set of minimal models in Ω' .

A mapping of an epistemic state Ψ to a TPO \preceq_Ψ that maintains the belief set is called a faithful assignment. For more information see [KM91].

2.4 Conditional Knowledge Bases

With TPOs providing a semantics for plausibility considerations, *conditionals* [KI01] provide syntactic entities able to express plausible, defeasible rules “If A , then plausibly (usually, typically etc.) B ”. More formally, the language \mathcal{L}_Σ is extended to a conditional language $(\mathcal{L}|\mathcal{L})_\Sigma$ by introducing a conditional operator $|$ [KI01]:

$$(\mathcal{L}|\mathcal{L})_\Sigma = \{(B|A) \mid A, B \in \mathcal{L}_\Sigma\}.$$

Here A is called the *antecedent* or the *premise* of $(B|A)$, and B is the *consequent* of the conditional $(B|A)$. A set $\mathcal{R} \subseteq (\mathcal{L}|\mathcal{L})_\Sigma$ of finitely many conditionals is called *conditional knowledge base* over Σ .

Instead of a propositional binary interpretation, conditionals can be used to express three different truth values:

$$(B|A)(\omega) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{iff } \omega \models AB \text{ (verification),} \\ 0 & \text{iff } \omega \models A\bar{B} \text{ (falsification),} \\ u & \text{iff } \omega \models \bar{A} \text{ (unknown).} \end{cases}$$

This can be read in the sense of de Finetti's Theory of Probability [Fin37]: a formula is “known to be true” if a possible world ω satisfies AB , thus *verifying* the conditional $(B|A)$, it is “known to be false” if a possible world ω satisfies $A\bar{B}$, thus *falsifying* it or it is “unknown” if a world ω satisfies \bar{A} , thus not fulfilling the premise A , allowing for no application of the conditional. For a conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} , let $\Sigma(\mathcal{R})$ be the minimal set of variables of Σ in which all conditionals $r \in \mathcal{R}$ can be expressed.

TPOs can also be used to encode plausibility rankings for conditionals, where a TPO \preceq *accepts* a conditional $(B|A)$, denoted as $\preceq \models (B|A)$ if $AB \preceq A\bar{B}$ and a conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} is accepted by \preceq if all conditionals in \mathcal{R} are accepted by \preceq .

Example 2.4. Consider Example 2.3 with the TPO \preceq_{abc} defined on $\Sigma_{abc} = \{a, b, c\}$. A conditional $(\bar{c}|\bar{a}\bar{b})$ would be accepted by the TPO \preceq_{abc} but a conditional $(c|ab)$ would not, *i.e.*, $\preceq_{abc} \models (\bar{c}|\bar{a}\bar{b})$ but $\preceq_{abc} \not\models (c|ab)$, because $\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec_{abc} \bar{a}\bar{b}c$ but $abc \not\prec_{abc} ab\bar{c}$.

Establishing a connection between the frameworks presented in the Sections 2.2, 2.3, and 2.4 can now look like in Example 2.5. Here, a conditional knowledge base is considered, which is accepted by a TPO representing the epistemic state. Based on this TPO, the belief set can be extracted.

Example 2.5. Let $\Sigma_{birds} = \{p, b, f\}$ be a signature with the atoms having the following meaning, respectively: *being a penguin* (p), *being a bird* (b), and *being able to fly* (f). Let \mathcal{R}_{birds} be a conditional knowledge base with conditionals $\{(f|b), (b|p), (\bar{f}|\bar{p})\}$ with the meaning that *birds usually can fly* ($f|b$), *penguins usually are birds* ($b|p$), and *penguins usually cannot fly* ($\bar{f}|\bar{p}$). A TPO accepting this knowledge base can look like the following

$\bar{p}\bar{b}f, \bar{p}\bar{b}\bar{f}, \bar{p}b\bar{f} \prec_{birds} pb\bar{f}, \bar{p}b\bar{f} \prec_{birds} pbf, \bar{p}b\bar{f} \prec_{birds} p\bar{b}f$. The above TPO \preceq_{birds} expresses the plausibility order stating that flying birds that are not penguins are just as plausible as flying things that are neither birds nor penguins and non-flying things that are neither birds nor penguins. These three variants likewise represent the most plausible worlds of the situation under consideration, whereas penguins that fly but are not birds represent the most implausible scenario.

From this TPO, the theory $\mathcal{T}_{birds} = \text{Cn}(\{\bar{p} \wedge (\bar{b} \vee f)\})$ can be excerpted.

Syntax Splitting with Respect to Different Frameworks

Originating in the idea to prevent revision operators from delivering unsatisfactory results by the effects that new information might have on completely irrelevant knowledge in a theory \mathcal{T} , Parikh proposed a notion of syntax splitting [Par99].

Splitting a syntax means partitioning the signature Σ such that the beliefs over sub-signatures $\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_n$ are independent from each other. The partition of a set is defined as follows, whereby the individual subsets from which the partition is composed are called *cells*.

Definition 3.1 (Partition of a Set). The *partition* \mathcal{P} of a set \mathcal{S} is a collection of n disjoint subsets (cells) $\{P_1, \dots, P_n\}$ that satisfies the following three conditions:

1. \mathcal{P} does not contain the empty set: $\emptyset \notin \mathcal{P}$.
2. The union of all cells must equal the superset: $\bigcup_{P \in \mathcal{P}} P = \mathcal{S}$.
3. The intersection of any two cells is empty: $\forall P, P' \in \mathcal{P}, P \neq P' \mid P \cap P' = \emptyset$.

Note that splitting relevant from irrelevant knowledge can result in huge performance boosts and is, for example, useful in the context of collaborating agents with limited resources in multi-agent-systems [WJZ16]. In the specific context of this thesis, syntax splitting is used to reduce the overall complexity so that knowledge over a signature can be expressed with less data required, *e.g.*, the number of possible interpretations over a signature $\Sigma = \{a, b, c, d\}$ would be $2^4 = 16$ ($2^{|\Sigma|}$). If this signature can now be split into sub-signatures (*i.e.*, partitioned according to framework-specific syntax splitting rules), the possible interpretations decrease as well, *e.g.*, for a partition $\mathcal{P} = \{\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2, \Sigma_3\}$ with $\Sigma_1 = \{a\}$, $\Sigma_2 = \{b, c\}$, and $\Sigma_3 = \{d\}$, the number of possible interpretations could be halved as $2^1 + 2^2 + 2^1 = 8$, while preserving all the information. This reduction of interpretations results in a reduction of the models as well, *e.g.*, $\text{Mod}_{\Sigma_1}(b) = \emptyset$, $\text{Mod}_{\Sigma_2}(b) = \{bc, b\bar{c}\}$, $\text{Mod}_{\Sigma_3}(b) = \emptyset$ contrary to $\text{Mod}_{\Sigma}(b) = \{abcd, abc\bar{d}, ab\bar{c}d, ab\bar{c}\bar{d}, \bar{a}bcd, \bar{a}bc\bar{d}, \bar{a}b\bar{c}d, \bar{a}b\bar{c}\bar{d}\}$. Along with this, logical entailment can now be calculated more conveniently, as fewer models have to be taken into account, while in terms of TPOs, the reduction in the

number of interpretations means that fewer elements in a TPO need to be ordered preferentially.

Likewise, regarding conditional knowledge bases, the compilation time of both the knowledge base and queries increases exponentially with each atom in Σ [BKS19], which can be at least addressed with syntax splitting of conditional knowledge bases.

In [KIB17], Kern-Isberner and Brewka lift the axioms of Parikh and Peppas *et al.* to the level of epistemic states represented by TPOs and ranking functions, laying the foundations of computerised syntax splitting. One part of the present work is the provision of algorithms able to calculate all syntax splittings for a given TPO.

Parikh also noted that syntax splitting might have a wider application than just in belief change, which inspired [BHKI21; KIBB20] to name two studies relevant for this work. The syntax splitting of conditional knowledge bases in these works mentioned is the second part this thesis aims to address, providing an algorithm to calculate the unique finest syntax splitting for a given conditional knowledge base.

The following sections describe syntax splitting for belief sets, for TPOs, and for conditional knowledge bases.

3.1 Syntax Splitting for Belief Sets

Aside from the postulates, solely important for belief revision, Parikh delivered a definition for the splitting of a theory \mathcal{T} in which he stated that a theory \mathcal{T} is being composed from its \mathcal{T}_i in the sub-languages \mathcal{L}_i [Par99]. A generalisation of Parikh's definition of \mathcal{T} -splitting is provided by [HKB20], where $\dot{\cup}$ indicates a union of disjunctive sets, used here to highlight syntax splittings³.

Definition 3.2 (*\mathcal{T} -Splitting [Par99; HKB20]*). Let Σ be a signature and \mathcal{T} a belief set over Σ . A partitioning $\Sigma = \Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$ is a syntax splitting for \mathcal{T} , if there are formulae $A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{L}_\Sigma$ with $\mathcal{T} = \text{Cn}_\Sigma(\{A_1, \dots, A_n\})$ and $\Sigma(A_i) \subseteq \Sigma_i$ for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$.

In this case, $\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$ is called *\mathcal{T} -splitting*.

³In set theory $\dot{\cup}$ is known as *disjunctive union*, where a present intersection of the corresponding sets is no element of the united outcome. Since syntax splittings are partitions and their elements therefore have no non-empty intersections, the inherent meaning of $\dot{\cup}$ fits perfectly here.

Example 3.1. Consider Example 2.2 with $\Sigma_{abc} = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathcal{T} = \text{Cn}(\{a \wedge (b \vee \bar{b}) \wedge \bar{c}\})$. Then $\Sigma_{abc} = \Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \Sigma_2 \dot{\cup} \Sigma_3$ is a \mathcal{T} -splitting for $\Sigma_1 = \{a\}$, $\Sigma_2 = \{b\}$, and $\Sigma_3 = \{c\}$.

One part of Parikh's paper is of great importance for this work: the idea of a *unique finest* \mathcal{T} -splitting, denoted by $\mathcal{F} = (F_i)_{i \in I}$. A unique finest \mathcal{T} -splitting implies that for every other \mathcal{T} -splitting $(\Sigma_j)_{j \in J}$ with $|I| > |J|$ and $I, J = \{1, \dots, n\}$, each F_i is contained in some Σ_j .

Definition 3.3 (Refinements and Coarsenings). A partition \mathcal{P}' *refines* another partition \mathcal{P} , iff for every $P'_i \in \mathcal{P}'$ there is a $P_j \in \mathcal{P}$ such that $P'_i \subseteq P_j$. \mathcal{P}' is then called the *refinement* of \mathcal{P} [Par99; Pep+15]. The opposite way will be called the *coarsening* [Mak07] in this thesis, i.e., \mathcal{P} is the coarsening of \mathcal{P}' .

The coarsest splitting, i.e., the 1-element splitting, i.e., $\Sigma = \Sigma_1$, will be called the *trivial splitting* [CP00].

Proposition 3.1 (Unique finest \mathcal{T} -splitting [Par99]). Given a theory \mathcal{T} in the language \mathcal{L}_Σ , there is a unique finest \mathcal{T} -splitting of \mathcal{L}_Σ , called \mathcal{F} , i.e., one which refines every other \mathcal{T} -splitting.

The partition lattice in Figure 3.1 shows all possible partitions of a 4-element signature $\Sigma = \{a, b, c, d\}$. Note that according to Proposition 3.1, if $\{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c, d\}\}$ were the unique finest \mathcal{T} -splitting \mathcal{F} , then the other splittings would be $\{\{a\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$, $\{\{b\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$, $\{\{a, b\}, \{c, d\}\}$, and $\{a, b, c, d\}$, i.e., only the partitions left of \mathcal{F} with a connection to \mathcal{F} .

Fig. 3.1.: Partition lattice coarse to fine from left to right. In the first layer the 1-element partition, in the second layer the 2-element partitions, in the third layer the 3-element partitions, and in the fourth layer the 4-element partitions. The edges indicate refinements/coarsenings between direct adjacent layers.

However, syntax splitting for belief sets is not the focus of this thesis. For more information, particularly on syntax splitting for belief sets in the context of belief change, refer to [Par99; Mak07; KM07; Pep+15; APW19; Ara22].

3.2 Syntax Splitting for Total Preorders on Worlds

In [Pep+15], Peppas *et al.* used TPOs as constructs providing meta information for AGM revision. Kern-Isberner and Brewka went significantly beyond that by defining syntax splitting on actual epistemic states represented by TPOs, rather than just using them for meta information [KIB17].

They pointed out that marginalisation is the basic concept to realise techniques of epistemic syntax splitting. This enabled them to provide definitions capturing notions of marginalisation and syntax splitting for epistemic states represented by TPOs in general (and represented by ranking functions specifically, which will not be considered in this chapter).

Definition 3.4 (Marginalisation of TPOs [KIB17]). Let Σ be a signature and Ψ be an epistemic state with TPO \preceq_Ψ on $\Omega(\Sigma)$, and let $\Theta \subseteq \Sigma$ be a subset of the signature. The marginalisation of Ψ to Θ , denoted by $\Psi|_\Theta$, is defined via the induced TPO on $\Omega(\Theta)$:

$$\Psi|_\Theta = (\Omega(\Theta), \preceq_{\Psi|_\Theta}), \quad \omega_1^\Theta \preceq_{\Psi|_\Theta} \omega_2^\Theta \text{ iff } \omega_1^\Theta \preceq_\Psi \omega_2^\Theta \text{ for worlds } \omega_1^\Theta, \omega_2^\Theta \in \Omega(\Theta).$$

Note that the worlds of Θ on the right-hand side of the *iff* condition are considered as formulae over Σ . The TPO \preceq_Ψ restricted to Θ , denoted by $\preceq_{\Psi|_\Theta}$, is a unique TPO, which demands that the order of two worlds restricted to a subset $\Theta \subseteq \Sigma$ must stay the same, whether under the original TPO \preceq_Ψ or under the marginalised TPO $\preceq_{\Psi|_\Theta}$.

Example 3.2. Consider Example 2.3 with $\Sigma_{abc} = \{a, b, c\}$ and epistemic state Ψ_{abc} with TPO \preceq_{abc} :

$\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec ab\bar{c} \prec a\bar{b}c \prec abc, \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}, \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}c, \bar{a}bc.$ Let $\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2 \subseteq \Sigma$ be subsets of Σ_{abc} , where $\Sigma_1 = \{a, b\}$ and $\Sigma_2 = \{c\}$ such that $\Sigma_{abc} = \Sigma_1 \cup \Sigma_2$. Looked upon $\Sigma_2 = \{c\}$, it holds for all $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \Omega(\Sigma_2)$ that

$$\bar{c} \prec_{\Psi|_{\Sigma_2}} c \text{ iff } \bar{c} \prec_\Psi c.$$

The same holds for all $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \Omega(\Sigma_1)$ such that the marginalised TPOs $\preceq_{\Psi|_{\Sigma_1}}$ and $\preceq_{\Psi|_{\Sigma_2}}$ look like the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{a}\bar{b} \prec_{\Psi|\Sigma_1} ab \prec_{\Psi|\Sigma_1} \bar{a}\bar{b}, \bar{a}b, \\ \bar{c} \prec_{\Psi|\Sigma_2} c. \end{aligned}$$

Peppas *et al.* provided a notion of symmetrical difference between two worlds as the set of atoms over which those worlds disagree [Pep+15]. This concept was specified by Aravanis *et al.* in [APW19].

Definition 3.5 (Possible Worlds Difference [Pep+15; APW19]). The difference between two worlds $\omega, \omega' \in \Omega(\Sigma)$, denoted by $Diff(\omega, \omega')$, is the set of propositional variables over which the two worlds disagree; *i.e.*, the symmetric difference of ω and ω' . In symbols:

$$Diff(\omega, \omega') = \{q \in \Sigma : \omega \models q \text{ and } \omega' \models \bar{q}\} \cup \{q \in \Sigma : \omega \models \bar{q} \text{ and } \omega' \models q\}$$

Example 3.3 (see [APW19]). Let $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$ be a signature, and let $\omega = abc$ and $\omega' = \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$, be two worlds $\omega, \omega' \in \Omega(\Sigma)$. Then $Diff(\omega, \omega') = \{a, c\}$

Marginalisation of epistemic states and the ability to distinguish between two worlds enabled Kern-Isberner and Brewka to define syntax splitting for epistemic states represented by TPOs.

Definition 3.6 (Syntax Splitting for TPOs [KIB17; HKB20]). Let $\{\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_n\}$ be a partition of Σ and Ψ be an epistemic state defined on Σ with TPO \preceq_{Ψ} on $\Omega(\Sigma)$. For each $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$, define that part of ω that excludes exactly the i -part ω^i as

$$\widehat{\omega}^i = \bigwedge_{j \neq i} \omega^j \text{ with } i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\},$$

with ω^j as variable assignment of the variables in Σ_j as in ω .

$\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$ is a syntax splitting for the TPO \preceq_{Ψ} if the following condition holds for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and for all $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \Omega(\Sigma)$:

$$\widehat{\omega}_1^i = \widehat{\omega}_2^i \text{ implies } (\omega_1 \preceq_{\Psi} \omega_2 \text{ iff } \omega_1^i \preceq_{\Psi|\Sigma_i} \omega_2^i). \quad (3.1)$$

In this case, $\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$ will be called *TPO-splitting*.

Definition 3.6 states that the order prior to marginalisation should not differ from the marginalised order whenever the excluded part, *i.e.*, the not affected partition, is the same for two worlds. The ω^i can be seen as the reducts ω^{\ominus} in the sense of the definitions given in Section 2.1, where $\widehat{\omega}^i$ builds its complement in $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$ such that $\omega = \omega^i \widehat{\omega}^i$ with omitted \wedge -connector. Note that $\widehat{\omega}^i$ is the conjunction of the ω^j . The i -part corresponds to the way a signature is partitioned.

Example 3.4. Let $\Sigma_{abc} = \{a, b, c\}$ be a signature, and let Ψ_{abc} be an epistemic state defined on Σ_{abc} with a TPO $\preceq_{\Psi_{abc}}: abc\bar{c}, a\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec_{\Psi_{abc}} abc, a\bar{b}c, \bar{a}b\bar{c}, \bar{a}\bar{b}c \prec_{\Psi_{abc}} \bar{a}bc, \bar{a}\bar{b}c$.

Consider four partitions of Σ : $\mathcal{P}_1 = \{\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2, \Sigma_3\}$, $\mathcal{P}_2 = \{\Sigma_4, \Sigma_3\}$, $\mathcal{P}_3 = \{\Sigma_5, \Sigma_2\}$, and $\mathcal{P}_4 = \{\Sigma_1, \Sigma_6\}$ with $\Sigma_1 = \{a\}$, $\Sigma_2 = \{b\}$, $\Sigma_3 = \{c\}$, $\Sigma_4 = \{a, b\}$, $\Sigma_5 = \{a, c\}$, and $\Sigma_6 = \{b, c\}$.

Table 3.1 shows the corresponding i -parts for two worlds $\omega_1 = abc\bar{c}$ and $\omega_2 = abc$ and their $\widehat{\omega}^i$, signaling the *ceteris paribus* situation.

Tab. 3.1.: Disagreement over two worlds and associated $\widehat{\omega}^i$ for specific partitions of Σ

Partitions	ω_1^i	ω_2^i	$\widehat{\omega}^i$
\mathcal{P}_1	$\omega_1^3 = \bar{c}$	$\omega_2^3 = c$	$\widehat{\omega}_1^3 = a \wedge b = \widehat{\omega}_2^3$
\mathcal{P}_2	$\omega_1^3 = \bar{c}$	$\omega_2^3 = c$	$\widehat{\omega}_1^3 = ab = \widehat{\omega}_2^3$
\mathcal{P}_3	$\omega_1^5 = a\bar{c}$	$\omega_2^5 = ac$	$\widehat{\omega}_1^5 = b = \widehat{\omega}_2^5$
\mathcal{P}_4	$\omega_1^6 = b\bar{c}$	$\omega_2^6 = bc$	$\widehat{\omega}_1^6 = a = \widehat{\omega}_2^6$

Condition 3.1 in Definition 3.6 demands that whenever the excluded parts $\widehat{\omega}^i$, *i.e.*, the conjunction of all ω^j , *i.e.*, $\omega^{\bar{i}}$, is the same for two worlds, the original ordering of those two worlds must be the same as the marginalised ordering. To check if a partition is a TPO-splitting, every i -part must be identified and the orderings must be the same.

Note that, contrary to \mathcal{T} -splittings, a maximally fine TPO-splitting $\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \Sigma_2 \dot{\cup} \Sigma_3$ does not imply its coarsenings to be TPO-splittings as well, *i.e.*, $(\Sigma_1 \cup \Sigma_2) \dot{\cup} \Sigma_3$ does not have to be a TPO-splitting.

Lemma 3.1. Coarsenings of TPO-splittings do not necessarily have to be TPO-splittings as well.

Proof. Let $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$ be a signature, and let Ψ be an epistemic state with TPO

$$abc \prec_{\Psi} a\bar{b}c, \bar{a}bc \prec_{\Psi} abc \prec_{\Psi} \bar{a}b\bar{c} \prec_{\Psi} a\bar{b}\bar{c}, \bar{a}\bar{b}c \prec_{\Psi} \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}.$$

Then $\Sigma = \{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$ is a TPO-splitting, but $\Sigma = \{a, b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$ is no TPO-splitting. \square

Consistent with intuition there is no reverse implication either.

Lemma 3.2. Refinements of TPO-splittings do not necessarily have to be TPO-splittings as well.

Proof. Let $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$ be a signature, and let Ψ be an epistemic state with TPO

$$abc, \bar{a}\bar{b}c \prec_{\Psi} \bar{a}bc, a\bar{b}c, \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec_{\Psi} \bar{a}b\bar{c}, a\bar{b}\bar{c}.$$

Then $\Sigma = \{a, b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$ is a TPO-splitting, but $\Sigma = \{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$ is no TPO-splitting. \square

It follows directly from the combination of the Lemmata 3.1 and 3.2 that to compute all TPO-splittings for a TPO, it is not sufficient to consider only one splitting (*e.g.*, the maximal fine splitting), since it does not imply that its coarser partitions are splittings as well. Thus, all partitions possible over a signature must be considered, *e.g.*, each partition in Figure 3.1 for a 4-element signature. Consequently, the complexity for computing all TPO splittings coincides with the *bell numbers*⁴ [Bel34] counting the possible partitions of a set.

Note that in the counterexample in the proof of Lemma 3.1, the TPO has exactly two syntax splittings, *i.e.*, the trivial splitting $\Sigma = \{abc\}$ and $\Sigma = \{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$. In a 3-element partition lattice, there would be no path from $\{a, b, c\}$ to $\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$ via any of the second-tier partitions, but since $\{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}\}$ is not only a refinement of these 2-element partitions but also of $\{a, b, c\}$, it can be stated that $\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$ refines every other splitting. Even though it is the only non-trivial splitting of this particular TPO, it is not a unique finest TPO splitting in the sense of Parikh's notion of unique finest splitting, because not all of its coarsenings are TPO-splittings as well. However, there seems to be always one unique maximally fine splitting for a given TPO which refines every other TPO-splitting of said TPO.

Conjecture 3.1. If a TPO has a syntax splitting, then it has a finest splitting which refines every other splitting of the given TPO. Particularly only coarser partitions of the finest splitting can be TPO-splittings as well.

While the above conjecture holds for the finest splitting of a TPO, it does not necessarily hold for any coarser splitting, such that only coarsenings of said splitting can be splittings themselves, as Example 3.5 demonstrates.

⁴The bell number for an n -element set can be calculated using Dobinski's Formula: $B(n) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{i^n}{i!}$ [BW13], by using Peirce's Triangle [Pol03], or with the help of the *stirling numbers of the second kind* [Twe03], which in this thesis will be called *stirling subset numbers* following the convention of Knuth [Knu92].

Example 3.5. Let $\Sigma_{abcd} = \{a, b, c, d\}$ be a signature, and let Ψ_{abcd} be an epistemic state with TPO \preceq_{abcd} :

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 & & ab\bar{c}d & & & \bar{a}b\bar{c}d \\
 abcd & & ab\bar{c}\bar{d} & & \bar{a}b\bar{c}d & & \bar{a}b\bar{c}\bar{d} \\
 ab\bar{c}d & \prec & \bar{a}bcd & \prec & \bar{a}b\bar{c}d & \prec & \bar{a}b\bar{c}\bar{d} \\
 & & \bar{a}b\bar{c}d & & \bar{a}b\bar{c}d & & \bar{a}b\bar{c}\bar{d} \\
 & & \bar{a}b\bar{c}d & & \bar{a}b\bar{c}d & & \bar{a}b\bar{c}\bar{d}
 \end{array}$$

The TPO \preceq_{abcd} has the following five syntax splittings:

- (I) $\{a, b, c\} \dot{\cup} \{d\}$,
- (II) $\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c, d\}$,
- (III) $\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{c\} \dot{\cup} \{b, d\}$,
- (IV) $\{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\} \dot{\cup} \{a, d\}$,
- (V) $\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\} \dot{\cup} \{d\}$.

Although splitting (I) is a coarsening of the finest splitting (V), none of the other three splittings (II), (III), and (IV) are refinements of (I).

3.3 Syntax Splitting for Conditional Knowledge Bases

Syntax splitting for conditional knowledge bases means that a conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} splits into sub-bases \mathcal{R}_i over disjoint sub-languages, *i.e.*, $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \mathcal{R}_n$, $\mathcal{R}_i \subset (\mathcal{L}_i | \mathcal{L}_i)$, $\mathcal{L}_i = \mathcal{L}(\Sigma_i)$ for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $\Sigma_i \cap \Sigma_j = \emptyset$ for $i \neq j$ and $\Sigma_1 \cup \dots \cup \Sigma_n = \Sigma$. In [BHK121], Beierle *et al.* provided a definition for the splitting of a conditional knowledge base, which was specified in [HB22a].

Definition 3.7 (Syntax Splitting of \mathcal{R} (adapted from [BHK121] and [HB22a])). Let \mathcal{R} be a conditional knowledge base over a signature Σ . A partitioning $\{\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_n\}$ is a syntax splitting for \mathcal{R} if there is a partitioning $\{\mathcal{R}_1, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n\}$ of \mathcal{R} such that \mathcal{R}_i is a knowledge base over Σ_i for each $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$.

In this case, $\{\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_n\}$ will be called *\mathcal{R} -splitting* and denoted by $\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$.

Example 3.6 (Inspired by [KIBB20]). Let $\Sigma = \{p, b, f, e, s\}$ be a signature with the atoms having the following meaning, respectively: being a penguin (p), being a bird (b), being able to fly (f), being an eel (e), being able to swim (s), and let $\mathcal{R} = \{(f|b), (b|p), (f|p), (s|e)\}$ be a conditional knowledge base with the meaning

that birds usually can fly, penguins usually are birds, penguins usually cannot fly, and eels usually can swim.

$$\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_1 \dot{\cup} \mathcal{R}_2 \text{ with } \Sigma_1 = \{p, b, f\}, \Sigma_2 = \{e, s\}, \text{ and } \mathcal{R}_1 = \{(f|b), (b|p), (\bar{f}|p)\}, \\ \mathcal{R}_2 = \{(s|e)\}.$$

As can be seen in Example 3.6, the conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} splits into sub-bases $\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2$ over disjoint sub-languages $\Sigma_1 = \{p, b, f\}, \Sigma_2 = \{e, s\}$ with Σ_1 and Σ_2 sharing no atoms $\Sigma_1 \cap \Sigma_2 = \emptyset$.

One of the purposes of this thesis is to develop an algorithm to calculate the *unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting* for an arbitrary conditional knowledge base. Similar to the notion of a unique finest \mathcal{T} -splitting [Par99], a unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting must be an \mathcal{R} -splitting which refines every other \mathcal{R} -splitting. Note that contrary to Conjecture 3.1 the notion of a unique finest syntax splitting here corresponds to Parikh’s original notion, where every coarsening of the unique finest splitting is, without further constraints, a splitting itself.

Since conditionals encode defeasible rules “if A , then plausibly B ”, there is a certain connection between the atoms in A and B , not unlike the connection between the atoms in a material implication $A \Rightarrow B$. In the specific case of conditionals, a connection between formulae is expressed by the conditional operator “|” which implies the connection between the atoms from which the formulae are constructed.

In [Mak07], Makinson provides a definition for the protection of a relation R between elementary letters in a belief set, thus forming a path-relevance derived from Rodrigues [Rod98], in which he states that a splitting $\mathbf{E} = \{E_i\}_{i \in I}$ of K *protects* R *iff* whenever $(p, q) \in R$, then p, q are in the same cell E_i of \mathbf{E} . The protection of a relation basically means that the splitting must comply with the protected relation, such that there can be no atoms in distinct cells that are contained in the relation. Note that Makinson takes a belief set as a set of formulae and does not specifically presume said belief set to be deductively closed⁵. In fact, Rodrigues actually considered knowledge bases instead of deductively closed belief sets in the original paper [Rod98], which fits the purpose of this thesis even better.

Makinson’s notions of relevance allow for a very abstract treatment of syntax splitting for frameworks such as conditional knowledge bases. For instance, for the representation of relevance, the only thing that has to be defined is a connector between atoms, which indicates the relation in need to be protected, *i.e.*, which

⁵Note that due to deductively closed belief sets containing all tautologies, even for two atoms p, q irrelevant to each other, they are path-relevant since for instance in a belief set $\mathcal{T} = \text{Cn}(\{p, q\}), (p \vee \bar{p}) \Rightarrow (q \vee \bar{q}) \in \text{Cn}(\mathcal{T})$ [Mak07].

relations in a knowledge base are relevant in the context of a given problem. Makinson's epistemic relevance provides an even more abstract way to approach syntax splitting.

He states that there is no predetermined way of specifying relations between letters that need to be protected, but that it can be any relation which he calls carrying *epistemic information* about the atoms connected by the relation [Mak07]. He defines a notion of epistemic relevance in which a splitting \mathbf{E} of K protects a subset $K' \subseteq K$ iff it protects the relation R defined by putting $(p, q) \in R$ iff there is a formula $x \in K'$ containing both p and q [Mak07]. As first limiting case holds $K' = \emptyset$, which means that nothing is protected in K and as such the finest K' -protecting splitting is just the finest splitting of K coinciding with Parikh's cell-relevance, *i.e.*, Parikh-style syntax splitting. The second limiting case approaches when $K' = K$, where every formula is in some connection and epistemic relevance coincides with Rodrigues' path-relevance. It is then important to define the epistemic information that needs to be protected to respect epistemic relevance depending on the surrounding context. This way, Makinson's notion of epistemic relevance is a highly applicable tool for the consideration of relevance in knowledge representation. However, in the context of conditional knowledge bases it suffices to take K' as the knowledge base \mathcal{R} , *i.e.*, the case when $K' = K$ such that syntax splitting for conditional knowledge bases can be seen as path-relevance.

With Rodrigues' notion of path-relevance for knowledge bases and Makinson's generalisation and broadening of the concept of path-relevance, the definition in [Mak07] regarding the protection of some relation between letters can be lifted to the level of conditional knowledge bases, where the conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} represents exactly the subset K' , *i.e.*, the epistemic knowledge of the given situation with the conditionals $r \in \mathcal{R}$ representing the formulae $x \in K'$.

Definition 3.8 (CO-protection). Let \mathcal{R} be a set of conditionals, and let $|$ be the relation between atoms in the conditionals of \mathcal{R} , called the *conditional operator CO*. Let $P, Q \in \mathcal{L}_\Sigma$ be two formulae with atoms $p, q \in \Sigma$ and $p \in \Sigma(P)$ and $q \in \Sigma(Q)$. For every conditional $(Q|P)$ it follows that $(p, q) \in CO$. A splitting $\mathbf{C} = \{C_i\}_{i \in I}$ of \mathcal{R} *protects CO* iff whenever $(p, q) \in CO$, then p, q are in the same cell C_i of \mathbf{C} .

A syntax splitting according to Definition 3.7 is exactly what a *CO*-protecting syntax splitting means for conditional knowledge bases with $|$ being the relation to be protected such that each conditional can be expressed by a minimal sub-language. Additionally, Makinson uses his definition to state that K has a unique finest R -

protecting splitting for which proof can be found in [Mak07; MK06]. The corollary formulated by Makinson can directly be translated to the framework of conditional knowledge bases, which Corollary 3.1 expresses.

Corollary 3.1 (Unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting). Let \mathcal{R} be a conditional knowledge base. $\mathbf{C} = (C_i)_{i \in I}$ is the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting for \mathcal{R} if for every other \mathcal{R} -splitting $(\Sigma_j)_{j \in J}$ with $|I| > |J|$ and $I, J = \{1, \dots, n\}$, each C_i is contained in some Σ_j .

Since signature variables that are not related to other variables requiring protection are not included in $\Sigma(\mathcal{R})$, they are always included in a solitary cell of the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting which is captured in Corollary 3.2.

Corollary 3.2 (Remainder variables in Σ). Let \mathcal{R} be a conditional knowledge base over a signature Σ . Each atom $a \notin \Sigma(\mathcal{R})$ is contained alone in some cell $C \in \mathbf{C}$, *i.e.*, $\forall a \in \Sigma \setminus \Sigma(\mathcal{R}) \exists C \in \mathbf{C} : a \in C \wedge \nexists b \in \Sigma : b \in C$ and $b \neq a$.

Proof. According to Definition 3.8, atoms which are contained in the relation CO are relevant to each other. Since the atoms of Σ that are not elements of $\Sigma(\mathcal{R})$ are also not contained in CO , consequently they are irrelevant for all other elements of Σ . \square

Graphical Representation of \mathcal{R} -splittings

Conditionals allow for an intuitive visualisation of syntax splitting in the form of *undirected graphs*⁶, although only for small knowledge bases with few variables.

Definition 3.9 (Undirected graph). An *undirected graph* is a pair $\mathcal{G} = \langle \mathbf{V}, \mathcal{E} \rangle$, where \mathbf{V} is a set of *vertices* or *nodes* and $\mathcal{E} \subseteq \mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{V}$ is a set of node operators (v, w) , the *edges* of \mathcal{G} . \mathcal{E} is symmetric, *i.e.*, for all $v, w \in \mathbf{V}$: $(v, w) \in \mathcal{E} \Rightarrow (w, v) \in \mathcal{E}$.

Relationships between atoms in conditionals can be represented by assigning each atom to a node of the graph in which edges are formed if two atoms are contained in a conditional. Two atoms are connected by an edge in this setting *iff* there is a conditional in which both atoms occur, hence it is irrelevant whether the atoms in the conditionals are positive or negated. Both conditionals $(\bar{b}|\bar{a})$ and $(b|a)$ will be represented by the same pair (a, b) , which implies trivially (b, a) . It does not matter whether the conditionals in question are of the form $(b|a)$, $(b \vee c|a)$, or $(b|a \wedge c)$ either,

⁶Undirected hypergraphs would intuitively fit even better, but two-noded graphs are more in line with Rodrigues' path-relevance in terms of definition.

as their graph representation would be (a, b) for $(b|a)$, (a, b) , (a, c) , and (b, c) for $(b \vee c|a)$, or (a, b) , (c, b) , and (a, c) for $(b|a \wedge c)$.

This may help to visualise possible syntax splittings for conditional knowledge bases. Similar to the approach of the present thesis of representing syntax splitting of conditional knowledge bases in a straightforward and intuitive way, this concept has already been established more complex by [KIT18; Hey+21], where it is aimed to form a connection between abstract argumentation and conditional logic⁷. However, in the context of syntax splitting of conditional knowledge bases, the much simpler notion of graph representation of conditional knowledge bases provided here fully suffices.

Example 3.7. Consider Example 3.6 with $\Sigma = \{p, b, f, e, s\}$.

Let $\mathcal{R} = \{(f|b), (b|p), (\bar{f}|p)\}$ be a conditional knowledge base, and let $\mathcal{G} = \langle V, \mathcal{E} \rangle$ be an undirected graph, where $V = \{p, b, f, e, s\}$ and $\mathcal{E} = \{(b, f), (p, f), (p, b)\}$.

Let $\mathcal{R}' = \mathcal{R} \cup \{(s|e)\}$ be a conditional knowledge base, and let $\mathcal{G}' = \langle V, \mathcal{E}' \rangle$ be an undirected graph, where $V = \{p, b, f, e, s\}$ and $\mathcal{E}' = \mathcal{E} \cup \{(e, s)\}$.

Let $\mathcal{R}'' = \mathcal{R}' \cup \{(s|p)\}$ be a knowledge base, and let $\mathcal{G}'' = \langle V, \mathcal{E}'' \rangle$ be an undirected graph, where $V = \{p, b, f, e, s\}$ and $\mathcal{E}'' = \mathcal{E}' \cup \{(p, s)\}$. Those three conditional knowledge bases can be visualised as in Figure 3.3.

⁷For more information see <http://car.mthimm.de>.

Fig. 3.3.: Different \mathcal{R} -splittings as undirected graphs. The edges represent the conditionals.

It is straightforward to see that in Figure 3.2a the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting consists of three cells, *i.e.*, $\mathbf{C} = \{p, b, f\} \dot{\cup} \{e\} \dot{\cup} \{s\}$.

Accordingly, in Figure 3.2b two cells, *i.e.*, $\mathbf{C}' = \{p, b, f\} \dot{\cup} \{e, s\}$ and in Figure 3.2c just one cell remains, as all five atoms have a connection to each other via their corresponding conditionals, such that there are no sub-bases \mathcal{R}_i'' that share no common variables of Σ , *i.e.*, $\mathbf{C}'' = \{p, b, f, e, s\}$.

However, the visualisation of conditional knowledge bases as undirected graphs is only an aid to illustration and has no further purpose for this thesis. Nevertheless, the connections between the nodes in the set \mathcal{E} provide an intuition of how \mathcal{R} -splitting might formally work if one considers these connections in terms of Rodrigues' notion of path-relevance [Rod98], which shows an approach to realising syntax splitting for conditional knowledge bases by considering these path-relevant formulae as non-divisible.

Example 3.8. Consider Example 3.7 with $\mathcal{R}'' = \{(f|b), (b|p), (\bar{f}|p), (s|e), (s|p)\}$ and $\mathcal{G}'' = \langle V, \mathcal{E}'' \rangle$. $V = \{p, b, f, e, s\}$ and $\mathcal{E}'' = \{(b, f), (p, f), (p, b), (e, s), (p, s)\}$. As per Definition 3.9, $(v, w) \in \mathcal{E} \Rightarrow (w, v) \in \mathcal{E}$, a path can be formed between f and e via $(p, f), (p, s)$, and (e, s) through $(p, f) \in \mathcal{E}'' \Rightarrow (f, p) \in \mathcal{E}'', (p, s)$, and $(e, s) \in \mathcal{E}'' \Rightarrow (s, e) \in \mathcal{E}''$, hence f and e are path-relevant to each other.

Similar to Definition 3.8 and Corollary 3.1, \mathcal{E} can be viewed as the relation needed to be protected by the syntax splitting such that if \mathbf{C} of \mathcal{R} protects \mathcal{E} , then \mathbf{C} is a syntax splitting and if \mathbf{C} is maximal in the sense of cardinality of cells, then \mathbf{C} is the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting.

Approaching Algorithmic Syntax Splitting for Total Preorders and Conditional Knowledge Bases

The main purpose of this work is to provide algorithms for the computation of syntax splittings for the frameworks of TPOs and conditional knowledge bases as well as the implementation of said algorithms. This chapter deals with the theoretical aspects and the formulation of the algorithms.

Chapter 3 established fundamentals and some first insights of what issues have to be taken into account. Coarsenings of TPO-splittings, for example, do not necessarily have to be splittings themselves, but in the framework of conditional knowledge bases this assertion can be made, since conditional knowledge bases do have unique finest \mathcal{R} -splittings.

In the context of TPO splittings, any marginalisation of the TPO under consideration must be computed, whereas for the splitting of conditional knowledge bases it is sufficient to consider the transitive closure of formulae in the conditionals, which is consistent with Makinson's epistemic relevance on the basis of Rodrigues' path-relevance. These properties have a specific influence on how an algorithmic approach can be made.

The following sections elaborate specifics about the automated calculation of TPO-splittings and the unique finest syntax splitting for a conditional knowledge base.

4.1 TPO-Splitting

A fundamental task in algorithm design is the modelling of a problem such that it can be approached with an algorithm fitting the desired purpose [Ski08]. With a problem such as syntax splitting of epistemic states, an enormous combinatorical complexity arises, so that algorithms must be designed as efficiently as possible.

The first step towards automatising syntax splitting for TPOs is to define what entities need to be calculated. According to Definition 3.6, a sub-signature $\Sigma_i \subseteq \Sigma$ can be considered *splittable*⁸ if Condition 3.1 in Definition 3.6 is met for all corresponding $\omega_i \in \Omega(\Sigma_i)$. This follows the intuition that even if the beliefs over $\Sigma_i \subseteq \Sigma$ are independent from the beliefs of another $\Sigma_j \subseteq \Sigma$ with $\Sigma = \Sigma_1 \cup \dots \cup \Sigma_n$, $i, j = \{1, \dots, n\}$, and $i \neq j$, it is not necessarily the case for the beliefs over $\Sigma_j \subseteq \Sigma$ with respect to the beliefs over $\Sigma_i \subseteq \Sigma$. However, for a partitioning $\{\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_n\}$ to be a splitting, all $\Sigma_i \subseteq \Sigma$ of the partitioning must satisfy Condition 3.1.

Definition 4.1 (Splittability). Let Σ be a signature, let Ψ be an epistemic state defined on Σ , and let $\{\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_n\}$ be an arbitrary partition of Σ . If for all $\omega^i \in \Omega(\Sigma_i)$ with $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ Condition 3.1 in Definition 3.6 holds, then the corresponding sub-signature $\Sigma_i \subseteq \Sigma$ is called *splittable*.

Example 4.1. Let $\Sigma_1 = \{b\}$, $\Sigma_2 = \{a, c\}$ be two cells of the partition $\Sigma = \Sigma_1 \cup \Sigma_2$. Let Ψ be an epistemic state with TPO $\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}, \bar{a}\bar{b}c \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}, \bar{a}bc \prec \bar{a}bc, \bar{a}b\bar{c}, abc, ab\bar{c}$. For this TPO $\Sigma_1 = \{b\}$ is splittable, *i.e.*, Condition 3.1 holds for all $\omega^1 \in \Omega(\Sigma_1)$, but its complement $\Sigma_2 = \{a, c\}$ in the partition $\{\{b\}, \{a, c\}\}$ is not splittable, *i.e.*, there are some $\omega^2 \in \Omega(\Sigma_2)$ for which Condition 3.1 does not hold.

As Example 4.1 shows, due to the splittability of $\Sigma_1 = \{b\}$, its complement in Σ , *i.e.*, $\Sigma_2 = \{a, c\}$ seems to be irrelevant to its beliefs, yet the converse is not true. But Definition 3.6 requires exactly that, so that none of the beliefs over the partitions depend on each other to form a syntax splitting.

In order to calculate all TPO-splittings of a given TPO, the splittability of all $\Sigma_i \subseteq \Sigma$ must now be calculated according to Definition 4.1. This requires looking at all the cells of each partition and checking for splittability. However, since all possible cells of a partition are contained in the second layer of the partition lattice, the observation can be made that there are recurrent Σ_i for different partitions, *i.e.*, for the TPO \preceq_{abcd} in Example 3.5 the Σ_1 for the partitions $\{\{a\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$ and $\{\{a\}, \{c\}, \{b, d\}\}$ is the same, *i.e.*, $\Sigma_1 = \{a\}$. This also means that to calculate the splittability of every single Σ_i , only the 2-element partitions⁹ have to be considered and the splittability of their cells has to be calculated. Lemma 4.1 is inspired by this observation.

⁸Note that Aravanis uses the term of *splittability* to state if a belief set has a syntax splitting [Ara22].

⁹Note that it would also suffice to look at the strict subsets of Σ , but the 2-element partitions of Σ carry useful information about the complements from which the $\hat{\omega}^i$ are formed.

Lemma 4.1. For the calculation of all splittable $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ over an arbitrary TPO only the 2-element partitions of Σ must be considered.

Proof. Consider any TPO. Each $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ is contained in some 2-element partition, hence all Σ_i of all n -element partitions of Σ with $n > 2$ can be constructed from these Σ_i 2-element partitions, thereby also affecting their property of being splittable or not splittable on the constructed n -element partitions. \square

Lemma 4.1 states that only the partitions in the second layer¹⁰ of the corresponding partition lattice must be considered as Σ_i . Every finer partition can be constructed from the already calculated Σ_i of the 2-element partitions. Table 4.1 elaborates this observation on a 4-element signature $\Sigma = \{a, b, c, d\}$, where it is not hard to verify that any $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ can be found at least twice (with the exception of the Σ_2 in the first four rows).

Tab. 4.1.: Partitions of Σ and visualisation of the Σ_i and their complements $\bar{\Sigma}_i$ in Σ

Partitions	Σ_1	$\bar{\Sigma}_1$	Σ_2	$\bar{\Sigma}_2$	Σ_3	$\bar{\Sigma}_3$	Σ_4	$\bar{\Sigma}_4$
$\{\{a\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{a\}$	-	-	-	-
$\{\{b\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{b\}$	-	-	-	-
$\{\{c\}, \{a, b, d\}\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{c\}$	-	-	-	-
$\{\{d\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{d\}$	-	-	-	-
$\{\{a, b\}, \{c, d\}\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{a, b\}$	-	-	-	-
$\{\{a, c\}, \{b, d\}\}$	$\{a, c\}$	$\{b, d\}$	$\{b, d\}$	$\{a, c\}$	-	-	-	-
$\{\{a, d\}, \{b, c\}\}$	$\{a, d\}$	$\{b, c\}$	$\{b, c\}$	$\{a, d\}$	-	-	-	-
$\{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c, d\}\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{c, d\}$	$\{a, b\}$	-	-
$\{\{a\}, \{c\}, \{b, d\}\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{b, d\}$	$\{a, c\}$	-	-
$\{\{a\}, \{d\}, \{b, c\}\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{b, c\}$	$\{a, d\}$	-	-
$\{\{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, d\}\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{a, d\}$	$\{b, c\}$	-	-
$\{\{b\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, c\}$	$\{b, d\}$	-	-
$\{\{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$	$\{a, b\}$	$\{c, d\}$	-	-
$\{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}\}$	$\{a\}$	$\{b, c, d\}$	$\{b\}$	$\{a, c, d\}$	$\{c\}$	$\{a, b, d\}$	$\{d\}$	$\{a, b, c\}$

It is straightforward to see that the need for $\{a\}$ as a cell can be found not only in the partition $\{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c, d\}\}$, but also in the first partition $\{\{a\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$, hence its property of being splittable does not have to be computed again and just has to be communicated. The same procedure can be applied to all other Σ_i , which inspired Lemma 4.2.

¹⁰The cardinality of the second layer of a partition lattice is given by the stirling subset numbers with $k = 2$ [Twe03; Knu92].

Lemma 4.2. If a partition of Σ can be constructed from splittable Σ_i , then this partition is a TPO-splitting.

Proof. Consider a partition of Σ which contains at least one Σ_i that is not splittable. It follows directly that this partition does not fulfill Condition 3.1, hence it is not a syntax splitting. \square

With Lemma 4.2, the TPO-splitting from Example 3.5 can now be explained.

Example 4.2. Continuation of Example 3.5. For this particular TPO, the following eight $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ are splittable (Condition 3.1 holds for those specific Σ_i):

1. $\Sigma_1 = \{a\}$,
2. $\Sigma_2 = \{b\}$,
3. $\Sigma_3 = \{c\}$,
4. $\Sigma_4 = \{d\}$,
5. $\Sigma_5 = \{a, d\}$,
6. $\Sigma_6 = \{b, d\}$,
7. $\Sigma_7 = \{c, d\}$,
8. $\Sigma_8 = \{a, b, c\}$.

From those $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$, the five syntax splittings as in Example 3.5 can be formed by combining them as distinct parts (partitions) of Σ . Here splitting (I) ($\{a, b, c\} \dot{\cup} \{d\}$) can be constructed by combining Σ_4 and Σ_8 , while splitting (V) ($\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\} \dot{\cup} \{d\}$) can be constructed by combining Σ_1 , Σ_2 , Σ_3 , and Σ_4 .

However, if there are not enough splittable $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ for the construction of a partition (*i.e.*, a TPO-splitting), those specific Σ_i serve no further purpose, as Example 4.3 demonstrates.

Example 4.3. Continuation of Example 4.1 with $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$ and an epistemic state Ψ defined on Σ with TPO over $\Omega(\Sigma)$. This TPO has the following splittable $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$:

1. $\Sigma_1 = \{a\}$,
2. $\Sigma_2 = \{b\}$,
3. $\Sigma_3 = \{a, b\}$,
4. $\Sigma_4 = \{b, c\}$.

From those splittable Σ_i only the partition $\{\{a\}, \{b, c\}\}$ can be constructed from Σ_1 and Σ_4 , hence $\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b, c\}$ is the only syntax splitting for this specific TPO.

The above findings can be summarised as the following two problems:

1. For the algorithmic calculation of all TPO-splittings for a given TPO, all splittable $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ have to be calculated.
2. All possible TPO-splittings have to be constructed from those splittable Σ_i .

Calculation of All Splittable Σ_i

Calculating the splittability of the $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ can be achieved by basically evaluating if Condition 3.1 holds for all possible $\omega^i \in \Omega(\Sigma_i)$. This can be represented by creating a table (*split-table*), where the row headers consist of two worlds $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \Omega(\Sigma)$ being compared and the column headers consist of the $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$. In each row there has to be evaluated if the corresponding $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ is splittable or not which is achieved by evaluating for each two worlds if Condition 3.1 holds. Tables 4.2 and 4.3 elaborate this concept, with Table 4.2 representing the TPO in question and its marginalised TPOs on $\Omega(\Sigma)$ with $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$, while Table 4.3 represents, with the split-table of the TPO presented in Table 4.2, a scheme of the suggested approach, where $\Sigma_1 = \{a\}$, $\Sigma_2 = \{b\}$, $\Sigma_3 = \{c\}$, $\Sigma_4 = \{a, b\}$, $\Sigma_5 = \{a, c\}$, and $\Sigma_6 = \{b, c\}$.¹¹

¹¹Note that the $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ are exactly the elements of the powerset $\mathcal{P}(\Sigma)$ minus Σ itself and the empty set.

Tab. 4.2.: Marginalised TPOs in row 2 for the TPO in row 1

\preceq	abc	\preceq	$\frac{a\bar{b}\bar{c}}{\bar{a}bc}$	\preceq	$ab\bar{c}$	\preceq	$\bar{a}b\bar{c}$	\preceq	$\frac{a\bar{b}\bar{c}}{\bar{a}bc}$	\preceq	$\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$
$\preceq_{ \Sigma_i}$	a	\preceq	\bar{a}								
	b	\preceq	\bar{b}								
	c	\preceq	\bar{c}								
	ab	\preceq	$\frac{a\bar{b}}{\bar{a}b}$	\preceq	$\bar{a}\bar{b}$						
	ac	\preceq	$\bar{a}\bar{c}$	\preceq	$a\bar{c}$	\preceq	$\bar{a}\bar{c}$				
	bc	\preceq	$\bar{b}\bar{c}$	\preceq	$b\bar{c}$	\preceq	$\bar{b}\bar{c}$				

Note that the worlds in the marginalised TPOs in Table 4.2 are seen as formulae over Σ .

Tab. 4.3.: Split-table and verification of the splittability of all $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ with $i \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$ for the given TPO in Table 4.2. The indicator for the marginalisation $|_i$ in the cells is omitted due to space issues. Columns 5, 6, and 7 evaluate to **false** due to Condition 3.1 not holding in the rows 24, 27, and 25 as the red colouring indicates, hence $\Sigma_4 = \{a, b\}$, $\Sigma_5 = \{a, c\}$, and $\Sigma_6 = \{b, c\}$ are not splittable.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7							
	ω_1	ω_2	$\Sigma_1 = \{a\}$	$\hat{\omega}^1$	$\Sigma_2 = \{b\}$	$\hat{\omega}^2$	$\Sigma_3 = \{c\}$	$\hat{\omega}^3$	$\Sigma_4 = \{a, b\}$	$\hat{\omega}^4$	$\Sigma_5 = \{a, c\}$	$\hat{\omega}^5$	$\Sigma_6 = \{b, c\}$	$\hat{\omega}^6$
2	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	$b \prec \bar{b}$	ac	-	-	$ab \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	c	-	-	$bc \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	a	
3	$abc \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	$a \prec \bar{a}$	bc	-	-	-	-	$ab \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	c	$ac \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	b	-	-	
4	$abc \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	$c \prec \bar{c}$	ab	-	-	-	$ac \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	b	$bc \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	a	
5	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	$ac \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	b	-	-	
6	$abc \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	$bc \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	a	
7	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	$ab \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	c	-	-	-	-	
8	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
9	$abc \sim \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	$ab \sim \bar{a}\bar{b}$	c	-	-	-	-	
10	$abc \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	$\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec b\bar{c}$	a	
11	$abc \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
12	$abc \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	$c \prec \bar{c}$	$\bar{a}\bar{b}$	-	-	$ac \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	\bar{b}	$\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	a		
13	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	$a \prec \bar{a}$	$\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	$ab \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	c	$ac \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	\bar{b}	-	-	
14	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	$ac \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	\bar{b}	-	-	
15	$abc \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	$\bar{a}\bar{c} \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	b	-	-	
16	$abc \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	$c \prec \bar{c}$	$\bar{a}\bar{b}$	-	-	-	$\bar{a}\bar{c} \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	b	$bc \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	\bar{a}	
17	$abc \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
18	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	$b \prec \bar{b}$	$\bar{a}\bar{c}$	-	-	$\bar{a}\bar{b} \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	c	-	-	$bc \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	\bar{a}	
19	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	$bc \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	\bar{a}	
20	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	$a \prec \bar{a}$	$\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	$ab \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	\bar{c}	$a\bar{c} \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	b	-	-	
21	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	$b \prec \bar{b}$	$a\bar{c}$	-	-	$ab \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	\bar{c}	-	-	$\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	a	
22	$abc \prec \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
23	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	$ab \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	\bar{c}	-	-	-	-	
24	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	$\bar{a}\bar{b} \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	\bar{c}	-	-	-	-	
25	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	$\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	\bar{a}	
26	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	$b \prec \bar{b}$	$\bar{a}\bar{c}$	-	-	$\bar{a}\bar{b} \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	\bar{c}	-	-	$\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	\bar{a}	
27	$abc \sim \bar{a}b\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	$a\bar{c} \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	\bar{b}	-	-	
28	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	$a \prec \bar{a}$	$\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	-	$\bar{a}\bar{b} \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}$	\bar{c}	$a\bar{c} \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	\bar{b}	-	-	
29	$abc \prec \bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	-	-	-	$c \prec \bar{c}$	$\bar{a}\bar{b}$	-	-	-	$\bar{a}\bar{c} \prec \bar{a}\bar{c}$	\bar{b}	$\bar{b}\bar{c} \prec \bar{b}\bar{c}$	\bar{a}	
30	splittable	true	true	true	true	true	true	false	false	false	false	false	false	

Table 4.3 shows for every relation between the worlds in the TPO if the marginalised TPO with excluded $\widehat{\omega}^i$ satisfies Condition 3.1. As can be seen, the Σ_i with $i \in \{4, 5, 6\}$ are not splittable and therefore cannot be used to construct syntax splittings. The Σ_i with $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ are splittable, hence the partition $\{\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2, \Sigma_3\}$ is a syntax splitting, while the partitions $\{\Sigma_1, \Sigma_6\}$, $\{\Sigma_2, \Sigma_5\}$, and $\{\Sigma_3, \Sigma_4\}$ are not.

With a split-table such as Table 4.3 the formulation of an algorithm to calculate the splittable Σ_i can be done in a straightforward way by using the map data type with Σ_i representing the key and a `boolean` value indicating if Σ_i is splittable or not as the value. What can be seen is in fact that an algorithm does not even have to calculate any more cells of a column once the condition does not hold. Since all $\omega^i \in \Omega(\Sigma_i)$ have to meet Condition 3.1 for the corresponding Σ_i to evaluate to `true` and only one ω^i not meeting the condition results in falsifying the splittability of said Σ_i , it suffices to assume Σ_i to be splittable and to stop the calculation, once the condition is not met. However, simply negating the implication in Condition 3.1 (*i.e.*, $(\omega_1 \preceq_{\Psi} \omega_2 \text{ iff } \omega_1^i \preceq_{\Psi|\Sigma} \omega_2^i)$) would lead to miscalculations, which is why the algorithm is provided with specific conditions that deviate slightly from Condition 3.1. As soon as the algorithm reached its goal of calculating the splittability of all Σ_i , it shall return only those Σ_i with the value `true`.

Algorithm 1 achieves all that and returns a list of splittable Σ_i as shown in Examples 4.2 and 4.3:

Algorithm 1 SPLITTABLESIGMA to calculate all splittable Σ_i for the given TPO.

Input: A TPO \preceq over a set of interpretations $\Omega(\Sigma)$.

Output: Set of all splittable $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$.

```

SplittingCandidates  $\leftarrow$  {} ▷ Initialise map with splitting candidates.
for all  $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$  do
    SplittingCandidates[ $\Sigma_i$ ]  $\leftarrow$  true ▷ Assume  $\Sigma_i$  is splittable.
    for all  $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \Omega(\Sigma)$  do
        if  $\widehat{\omega}_1 = \widehat{\omega}_2$  then
            if  $\neg($ 
                 $(\omega_1 \prec_{\Omega(\Sigma)} \omega_2 \wedge \omega_1^i \prec_{\Omega(\Sigma_i)} \omega_2^i) \vee$ 
                 $(\omega_1 \succ_{\Omega(\Sigma)} \omega_2 \wedge \omega_1^i \succ_{\Omega(\Sigma_i)} \omega_2^i) \vee$ 
                 $(\omega_1 \sim_{\Omega(\Sigma)} \omega_2 \wedge \omega_1^i \sim_{\Omega(\Sigma_i)} \omega_2^i)$ 
            ) then
                SplittingCandidates[ $\Sigma_i$ ]  $\leftarrow$  false ▷  $\Sigma_i$  is not splittable.
                break
            end if
        end if
    end for
end for
return SplittingCandidates with value true.

```

Construction of All TPO-splittings from Splittable Σ_i

With the knowledge of which $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ are splittable, the second problem mentioned above can be approached. Having a number of *items* (*i.e.*, splittable Σ_i) and a target *capacity* (*i.e.*, $|\Sigma|$), this problem can be modelled as a *subset-sum problem* which is a special case of the *knapsack problem*.¹² In its original meaning the subset-sum problem determines whether or not a subset from a list of integers (*weights* of items) can sum to a specific target value (capacity of the knapsack).

Example 4.4. Consider a list of integers $[1, 2, 3, 4, 5]$ and a target sum = 8. There exists at least one subset of the list of integers whose sum equals the given target sum, hence this subset-sum problem can be solved.

However, it is not enough just to know whether there is a solution to solve the above problem, but to enumerate all possible solutions, *e.g.*, there are three solutions to the subset-sum problem in Example 4.4: $\{1, 2, 5\}$, $\{1, 3, 4\}$, and $\{3, 5\}$.

In the context of TPO-splittings, $|\Sigma|$ represents the capacity of the knapsack, while the splittable Σ_i represent the elements with $|\Sigma_i|$ representing their weights. In addition, the constraint that the solutions must be partitions of Σ needs to be satisfied, such that although many subset-sum solutions can be found in general, not all of them might be partitions of Σ .

Example 4.5. Continuation of Example 4.3 with $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$ and the splittable $\Sigma_i \in \{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}\}$.

The weights of these splittable Σ_i correspond to their cardinality, *i.e.*, $|\{a\}| = 1$, $|\{b\}| = 1$, $|\{a, b\}| = 2$, and $|\{b, c\}| = 2$, while the capacity of the knapsack is $|\Sigma| = 3$. Hence the list of considered integers as in Example 4.4 in this case is $[1_a, 1_b, 2_{ab}, 2_{bc}]$ and the target sum is 3 for which there are four subset-sum solutions $\{\{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$, $\{\{a\}, \{b, c\}\}$, $\{\{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$, and $\{\{b\}, \{b, c\}\}$. However, it does not suffice to look just at the weights of the splittable Σ_i but also at their combination being a partition of Σ which yields in this case only one solution: $\{\{a\}, \{b, c\}\}$ with $|\{a\}| + |\{b, c\}| = 3$.

Solutions of this modified subset-sum problem can be visualised as undirected hypergraphs.

¹²This problem could also be solved by an exact-cover or a set-packing approach which have similar runtime complexity [MT90; Ski08; KV18], but due to the wider applicability of subset-sum (OCF-splitting, Section 7.2) and the possibility to reduce the runtime complexity of knapsack problems through *dynamic programming*, these approaches have not been pursued.

Definition 4.2 (Undirected hypergraph). An *undirected hypergraph* is a pair $\mathcal{H} = \langle \mathbf{V}, \mathcal{E} \rangle$, where \mathbf{V} is a set of nodes, and \mathcal{E} is (in an undirected hypergraph) a set of non-empty subsets of \mathbf{V} called *hyperedges*.

Each hyperedge represents one (true) solution of the subset-sum problem in this setting, *i.e.*, each hyperedge represents one syntax splitting for the given TPO with which one knapsack each can be filled. Figure 4.1 shows how such a collaboration of knapsack and hypergraph in the context of TPO syntax splitting can look like. The hypergraph \mathcal{H}_{abcd} in Figure 4.1a has the elements $\mathbf{V}_{abcd} = \{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{abcd} = \{\{\{a, b, c\}, \{d\}\}, \{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c, d\}\}, \{\{a\}, \{c\}, \{b, d\}\}, \{\{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, d\}\}, \{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}\}\}$. The hypergraph \mathcal{H}_{abc} in Figure 4.1b has the elements $\mathbf{V}_{abc} = \{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}\}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{abc} = \{\{a\}, \{b, c\}\}$.

(a) Knapsack solutions for the spittable Σ_i in Example 4.2 with $\Sigma = \{a, b, c, d\}$

(b) Knapsack solution for the spittable Σ_i in Example 4.5 with $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$

Fig. 4.1.: Representation of TPO-splittings as hypergraphs \mathcal{H}_{abcd} and \mathcal{H}_{abc} , where each hyperedge fills exactly one knapsack.

With the knapsack problem—and as such the subset-sum problem—being an NP-hard problem [Kar72], there exists no efficient algorithm to solve it. Although knapsack problems being NP-hard, they are not *strongly* NP-hard problems and there does exist an algorithm with pseudopolynomial running time using dynamic programming [Bel56; Ski08] which reduces runtime complexity to $\mathcal{O}(nC)$, where n is the number of subsets and C is the capacity of the knapsack. Note that this approach comes with additional auxiliary space complexity of $\mathcal{O}(C)$ which is why it has to be evaluated if dynamic programming really is the best practice for solving a specific knapsack problem. If all the sizes are relatively small integers (*e.g.*, $C < 1,000$), it is fairly reasonable to use dynamic programming [Ski08]. Considering that a propositional signature Σ of size 1,000 would have a universe $\Omega(\Sigma)$ of size $2^{1,000}$, it is unrealistic to calculate syntax splittings for a corresponding TPO, since the complexity of calculating the splittability of all $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ alone starting from $|\Omega(\Sigma)|$ would again grow exponentially¹³.

Approaching the subset-sum problem with dynamic programming, a table (*dp-table*) needs to be created which stores the *state* of the calculation (*i.e.*, if the target sum is reached or if it is still reachable or if it is not). The dp-table will have as many rows as there are splittable Σ_i , here denoted with n , and $|\Sigma| + 1$ columns.

On row i all subsets using integers up to and including the i -th integer (although it does not necessarily need to be included) are being considered. Since there are columns with $|\Sigma| + 1$, the final value of j will be $|\Sigma|$, which means that in the end subsets must be found that sum to $j = |\Sigma|$. Therefore $\text{dp-table}[i][j] = \text{true}$ means that there is a subset in the splittable Σ_i whose sum results in j . If $\text{dp-table}[i][j] = \text{false}$, there is no such subset. The solution can be recovered if $\text{dp-table}[n-1][|\Sigma|] = \text{true}$, so that there is a subset in the splittable Σ_i that gives the sum of $|\Sigma|$.

¹³For $|\Sigma| = 1,000$ there would be $1.071 \cdot 10^{301}$ $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ that would have to be checked if they are splittable or not.

Example 4.6. Continuation of Example 4.5 with $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$ and the splittable $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ being $\{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}\}$. The according dp-table could look like Table 4.4.

Tab. 4.4.: A dp-table representing the presence of at least one solution for the subset-sum problem corresponding to the TPO as in Example 4.5 with abbreviated `boolean` values, where T means `true` and F means `false`.

	0	1	2	3
$ a $	T	T	F	F
$ b $	T	T	T	F
$ a, b $	T	T	T	T
$ b, c $	T	T	T	T

The greatest column header being 3 matches the cardinality of Σ , *i.e.*, $|\Sigma| = 3$. When `dp-table[i][0]` is considered, the current target sum = 0 can be reached with all four subsets, since $|\emptyset| = 0$. Due to $j = 1$ being reachable with $|a|$, `dp-table[0][1]` is `true`, but `dp-table[0][2]` is `false` because the considered set of subsets here consists of only $|a| \neq 2$. The same can be applied for `dp-table[0][3]`. With $|a|$ and $|b|$ `dp-table[1][2] = true` ($|a| + |b| = 2$). However, the initial target sum of $|\Sigma|$ still cannot be reached with only $|a|$ and $|b|$. The first possible subset-sum solution arises with `dp-table[2][3]` when the considered subsets consist of $|a|$, $|b|$, and $|a, b|$, where with $|a, b|$ and either $|a|$ or $|b|$ the target sum of 3 can be reached ($|a| + |a, b| = |b| + |a, b| = 3$). The same applies for `dp-table[3][3]`.

Following [MT90] and [KV18], an algorithm can be formulated that fills the dp-table in the above manner. Algorithm 2 serves this purpose precisely starting with an empty array of splittable Σ_i or in short `sSA`, that is being filled with the truth values whether a current target sum j is reachable with the considered subsets or not.

Algorithm 2 FILLDPTABLE Algorithm to fill the dp-table for the given subset-sum problem in order to calculate whether there is a splitting for the given TPO or not.

Input: An array consisting of all splittable Σ_i and $|\Sigma|$.

Output: A dp-table filled with `boolean` values.

```

sSA[]  $\leftarrow$  SPLITTABLESIGMA( $\preceq_{\Omega(\Sigma)}$ )
dp-table  $\leftarrow$  boolean[|sSA|][ $|\Sigma| + 1$ ] ▷ 2D-Array for current state.
for all  $\Sigma_i \in$  sSA do
  | dp-table[i][0]  $\leftarrow$  true ▷  $|\emptyset| = 0$ .
end for
if |sSA[0]| <  $|\Sigma|$  then
  | dp-table[0][|sSA[0]|]  $\leftarrow$  true
end if
for all  $i \in \{0, \dots, |sSA| - 1\}$  do
  | for all  $j \in \{0, \dots, |\Sigma|\}$  do
  | | if |sSA[i]|  $\leq j$  then
  | | | dp-table[i][j]  $\leftarrow$  dp-table[i - 1][j]  $\vee$  dp-table[i - 1][j - |sSA[i]|]
  | | else dp-table[i][j]  $\leftarrow$  dp-table[i - 1][j]
  | | end if
  | end for
end for
return dp-table ▷ Filled dp-table.

```

What Algorithm 2 achieves is the solution of the basic subset-sum problem, but as can be seen in Example 4.6, there are at least two solutions as Table 4.4 indicates. However, as stated above, only the knowledge if there is a solution is not the specified goal of constructing all TPO-splittings from the splittable Σ_i , but enumerating all possible solutions and filtering out those which are not partitions of Σ . For the enumeration of all possible solutions, the dp-table must be recursively traversed by consideration of four possible cases:

- (a) The length of the considered subset is 0 and `dp-table[0][j] = true`;
- (b) the length of the considered subset at $i = 0$ and the current target sum $j = 0$;
- (c) `dp-table[i - 1][j] = true`;
- (d) j is greater than or equal to the considered subset and `dp-table[i - 1][j - $|\Sigma_i|$] = true`.

In cases (a) and (b) the solutions must be collected and stored somewhere, while in cases (c) and (d), the dp-table must be traversed further.

Table 4.5 shows the four possible paths through the dp-table representing the four solutions for the given subset-sum problem as in Example 4.5.

Tab. 4.5.: Possible paths through the dp-table, which represent the solutions for the subset-sum problem corresponding to the TPO as in Example 4.5.

(a) Path to solution $\{\{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$

	0	1	2	3
$ a $	T	T	F	F
$ b $	T	T	T	F
$ a, b $	T	T	T	T
$ b, c $	T	T	T	T

(b) Path to solution $\{\{a\}, \{b, c\}\}$

	0	1	2	3
$ a $	T	T	F	F
$ b $	T	T	T	F
$ a, b $	T	T	T	T
$ b, c $	T	T	T	T

(c) Path to solution $\{\{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$

	0	1	2	3
$ a $	T	T	F	F
$ b $	T	T	T	F
$ a, b $	T	T	T	T
$ b, c $	T	T	T	T

(d) Path to solution $\{\{b\}, \{b, c\}\}$

	0	1	2	3
$ a $	T	T	F	F
$ b $	T	T	T	F
$ a, b $	T	T	T	T
$ b, c $	T	T	T	T

The Sub-tables 4.5a, 4.5b, 4.5c, and 4.5d show the paths to recover the four solutions to the subset-sum problem as in Example 4.5. Although the subset-sum solutions $\{\{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$, $\{\{a\}, \{b, c\}\}$, $\{\{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$, $\{\{b\}, \{b, c\}\}$ each yield $|\Sigma|$, *i.e.*, are valid solutions to the subset-sum problem, only the solution $\{\{a\}, \{b, c\}\}$ is a partition of $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$ and hence the only splitting of the corresponding TPO. The condition to collect only solutions that are partitions of Σ can be easily fulfilled by filtering out those solutions that violate one of the conditions in Definition 3.1.

Translated to the problem of constructing all TPO-splittings, the specific subset-sum problem can be treated as a sub-problem and performed only on the sizes of the splittable Σ_i , while the subsequent partition check is performed based on the splittable Σ_i themselves that are simply given to the method as parameter.

Algorithm 3 SPLITTINGKNAPSACK now calls FILLDPTABLE and traverses the dp-table recursively according to the rules specified above until all solutions have been found. In the two cases where a subset-sum solution has been found, it is first checked whether it is a partition of Σ . If it is, this solution is added to the list of splittings. After the current solution has been checked, the context is gone and thus the vector in which the solution is stored is cleared again.

This algorithm is abbreviated as follows to save space: the array with the splittable Σ_i as before is abbreviated with `sSA`, the list of final solutions, *i.e.*, the list with all TPO-splittings `listOfSplittings`, is abbreviated with `lSplit`, and the currently considered solution with `sol`.

Algorithm 3 SPLITTINGKNAPSACK Algorithm to recover all TPO-splittings for the given TPO from the given dp-table.

Input: A filled dp-table.

Output: Set of all TPO-splittings for a TPO \preceq over $\Omega(\Sigma)$.

```

dp-table  $\leftarrow$  FILLDPTABLE
SPLITTINGKNAPSACKREC(lSplit, sSA, |sSA| - 1, |\Sigma|, sol)  $\triangleright$  Initial call.
procedure SPLITTINGKNAPSACKREC(lSplit, sSA, |sSA|, |\Sigma|, sol)
  if |sSA| = 0  $\wedge$  |\Sigma|  $\neq$  0  $\wedge$  dp-table[0][|\Sigma|] = true then
    | sol  $\leftarrow$  sol + sSA[|sSA|]
    | if {sol1, ..., soln} is a partition of  $\Sigma$  then
    | | lSplit  $\leftarrow$  lSplit + sol  $\triangleright$  Collect and concatenate.
    | end if
    | return
  end if
  if |sSA| = 0  $\wedge$  |\Sigma| = 0 then
    | if {sol1, ..., soln} is a partition of  $\Sigma$  then
    | | lSplit  $\leftarrow$  lSplit + sol  $\triangleright$  Collect and concatenate.
    | end if
    | return
  end if
  if dp-table[|sSA| - 1][|\Sigma|] = true then
    | solRec  $\leftarrow$  sol
    | SPLITTINGKNAPSACKREC(lSplit, sSA, |sSA| - 1, |\Sigma|, solRec)
  end if
  if |\Sigma|  $\geq$  |sSA[|sSA|]|  $\wedge$  dp-table[|sSA| - 1][|\Sigma| - |sSA[|sSA|]|] = true then
    | sSA  $\leftarrow$  sSA + sSA[|sSA|]
    | SPLITTINGKNAPSACKREC(lSplit, sSA, |sSA| - 1, |\Sigma| - |sSA[|sSA|]|, sol)
  end if
end procedure
return lSplit  $\triangleright$  List of all splittings now filled with subset-sum solutions.

```

4.2 \mathcal{R} -Splitting

For the splitting of conditional knowledge bases, no marginalisation is required and interpretations do not need to be taken into account, rendering the performance considerations much less severe. Moreover, since there is a unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting for each conditional knowledge base, as shown in Section 3.3, which perfectly mirrors what Parikh has defined as a unique finest \mathcal{T} -splitting for belief sets, there is no need to compute all possible splittings for the conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} . It is sufficient here to compute only the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting of the given conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} , which can be realised by formulating an algorithm that finds the path-relevance between atoms of Σ in \mathcal{R} .

A reasonable approach to this is to put all variables, from which formulae are formed in the antecedent and consequent of a conditional, into a set for each conditional, *i.e.*, for each conditional $r \in \mathcal{R}$ let $\Sigma(r)$ be the minimal subset of atoms in which the corresponding conditional $r \in \mathcal{R}$ can be expressed. The result is a set of sets of atoms, each of which can be used to express the corresponding conditional $r \in \mathcal{R}$.

Definition 4.3 (Applicants of \mathcal{R} , $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$). Let \mathcal{R} be an arbitrary conditional knowledge base with conditionals $r \in \mathcal{R}$. The set of *applicants* ($\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$) denotes the set of sets of propositional atoms from which the conditionals are constructed, where the function $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ returns for an arbitrary conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} all subsets containing the propositional variables used in the conditionals $r \in \mathcal{R}$, *i.e.*, $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R}) = \{\Sigma(r) \mid \text{for all } r \in \mathcal{R}\}$.

According to Makinson's epistemic relevance [Mak07] in Definition 3.8, all atoms in the antecedent and the consequent of a conditional are path-relevant to each other, the conditional operator being the relation to be protected. Consequently, these elements must be in the same splitting cell, which $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ partially achieves. Those subsets of $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ with non-empty intersections must also be in the same cell of the unique finest syntax splitting.

The function $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ helps constructing a rudimentary splitting, which in some cases already represents the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting, but in other cases there are some subsets in $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ sharing letters, hence need to be combined.

According to this, the next step is to check for each pair of sets of atoms whether the sets have overlapping atoms, and if so, to combine these sets. If there are no more non-empty intersections between two sets, all that remains is a set of

minimal sub-signatures in which any set of conditionals relevant to each other can be expressed.

Example 4.7. Consider $\Sigma_{bfe s} = \{b, f, e, s\}$ and a conditional knowledge base $\mathcal{R}_{bfe s} = \{(f|b), (s|e)\}$. The applicants of $\mathcal{R}_{bfe s}$ are contained in the set $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R}_{bfe s}) = \{\{b, f\}, \{e, s\}\}$, which represents exactly the unique finest $\mathcal{R}_{bfe s}$ -splitting $\{b, f\} \dot{\cup} \{e, s\}$ for $\mathcal{R}_{bfe s}$, *i.e.*, $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R}_{bfe s}) = \mathbf{C}_{bfe s}$.

Example 4.8. On the other hand, consider $\Sigma = \{p, b, f, e, s\}$ and the knowledge base $\mathcal{R} = \{(f|b), (b|p), (f|\bar{p})\}$ of Example 3.7. The applicants of \mathcal{R} are contained in the set $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R}) = \{\{b, f\}, \{f, p\}, \{b, p\}\}$ which is not the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting $\mathbf{C} = \{p, b, f\} \dot{\cup} \{e\} \dot{\cup} \{s\}$, *i.e.*, $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R}) \neq \mathbf{C}$. Furthermore, $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ is not an \mathcal{R} -splitting at all, since firstly $\Sigma_i \cap \Sigma_j \neq \emptyset$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, $i \neq j$, and secondly, not all variables from Σ are included in $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$.

Lemma 4.3. If $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ is an \mathcal{R} -splitting, it is the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting.

Proof. Let $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ be the set of applicants of an arbitrary conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} , where for all $\Sigma(r), \Sigma(r') \in \text{appl}(\mathcal{R}) : \Sigma(r) \cap \Sigma(r') = \emptyset$, $r \neq r'$. Since each syntax splitting is a partition of Σ , any atom in Σ must be contained in $\Sigma(r)$ according to Definition 3.7, thus if $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ is an \mathcal{R} -splitting, then $\Sigma(\mathcal{R}) = \Sigma$. Finally, since there are no more path-relevant variables in different cells in $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$, it is the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting. \square

Lemma 4.3 indicates that in order to calculate the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting, $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ needs to be refined¹⁴ in the sense that it consists only of non-overlapping cells. Doing so can be achieved by checking each cell $\Sigma(r) \in \text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ whether it has a non-empty intersection with another cell $\Sigma(r') \in \text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$. If for some cells $\Sigma(r) \cap \Sigma(r') \neq \emptyset$, then those two must be exchanged with their union, *i.e.*, if $\Sigma(r) \cap \Sigma(r') \neq \emptyset$, $r \neq r'$, then $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R}) \leftarrow (\text{appl}(\mathcal{R}) \setminus \{\Sigma(r), \Sigma(r')\}) \cup (\{\Sigma(r) \cup \Sigma(r')\})$. The refined set $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ in Example 4.8 would then be $\{p, b, f\}$ which is exactly one cell of \mathbf{C} .

For an algorithmic approach, the array data type is suitable, whereby for two overlapping subsets of $\Sigma(r), \Sigma(r') \in \text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$, one of the two becomes the union, while the respective other is assigned the value `null`. Every applicant assigned the value `null` will be ignored in further iterations.

Algorithm 4 shows how the formulation of the just discussed approach can look like.

¹⁴Note that “refinement” has a different meaning here than it has solely in the context of partitions.

Algorithm 4 FINDPATHRELEVANCE Algorithm to exchange overlapping subsets in $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ with their union.

Input: Set of applicants $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$.

Output: Set of applicants $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ in refined form such that fewer elements of it overlap each other.

remove strict subsets in $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$

$\text{appl}[] \leftarrow \text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ ▷ Put applicants in an array.

for all $i \in \{0, \dots, |\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})|\}$ **do**

for all $j \in \{i + 1, \dots, |\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})|\}$ **do**

if $\text{appl}[i] = \text{null} \vee \text{appl}[j] = \text{null}$ **then** ▷ Ignore if either is null.
 | **continue**

end if

if $\text{appl}[i] \cap \text{appl}[j] \neq \emptyset$ **then**

$\text{appl}[i] \leftarrow \text{appl}[i] \cup \text{appl}[j]$

$\text{appl}[j] \leftarrow \text{null}$ ▷ To be ignored.

end if

end for

end for

return filtered and collected stream of $\text{appl}[]$ without **null** entries

Consequently, the algorithm must refine the set $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ until the sum of the cardinalities of its elements equals the cardinality of $\Sigma(\mathcal{R})$.

However, the refined set $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ does not necessarily correspond to the unique finest splitting, as can be seen in Example 4.8. If there are variables in Σ that are not in $\Sigma(\mathcal{R})$ and as such are not contained in any element of $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$, they will not be considered either by FINDPATHRELEVANCE, due to no relevant paths. Thus, in a final step and respecting Corollary 3.2, all variables not contained in $\Sigma(\mathcal{R})$ must be added to the refined set $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ as singleton sets. The whole process is started and finished with Algorithm 5.

Algorithm 5 SPLITKB Algorithm to compute the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting for a given signature Σ and a conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} .

Input: Set of applicants $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ as a set of sets of variables which represent the conditionals in \mathcal{R} .

Output: Unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting \mathbf{C} as set of sub-signatures $\{\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_n\}$.

applicants $\leftarrow \text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$

do

 | resultSet \leftarrow FINDPATHRELEVANCE(applicants)

while $\sum_{i=1}^n |\text{resultSet}_i| > |\Sigma(\mathcal{R})|$

$\mathbf{C} \leftarrow \text{resultSet} \cup \{e\} \mid \forall e \in (\Sigma \setminus \Sigma(\mathcal{R}))$ ▷ Add singleton remainders.

return unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting \mathbf{C} .

Augmenting InfOCF-Lib

The primary goal of this thesis is to implement the algorithms formulated in Chapter 4 into an existing system, namely `InfOCF-Lib` [Kut19].

The Java library `InfOCF-Lib` is a system that provides methods to compute and represent epistemic states represented by *ranking functions* (*ordinal conditional functions*, *OCFs*) [Spo88] from conditional knowledge bases.

Internally the system works with *c-representations* [KI01; KI04] which are a subset of all ranking functions for a knowledge base. Providing solutions for constraint satisfaction problems with respect to the knowledge base [Bei+18], *c-representations* can be calculated with little effort.

`InfOCF-Lib` as of now has no capabilities to read TPOs but can construct them from OCFs. However, to compute TPO-splittings, `InfOCF-Lib` must be extended to be able to read and represent TPOs. On top of the already existing functionalities to work with conditional knowledge bases, the algorithms for the calculation of the unique finest syntax splitting for conditional knowledge bases could be implemented with less effort.

The classes and functionalities developed in this chapter will be used to extend `InfOCF-Lib`, such that TPOs can be read and represented by `InfOCF-Lib` as well as to enable `InfOCF-Lib` to perform syntax splitting on TPOs and on conditional knowledge bases.

5.1 Relevance in a Different Context

Combinatorial complex problems such as partitioning or knapsack problems are usually accompanied by long runtimes. Due to the strong development of hardware in the last decades and the resulting multi-core processors, a lot of research and development has gone into the parallelisation of computerised tasks in order to process complex tasks concurrently—as far as possible—and thus reduce runtime. Though only those processes that are independent from each other and whose results are not relevant to each other can be parallelised.

In Java the possibility of concurrent and thus parallel programming was anchored directly in the language standard. However, these standard concepts are very rudimentary and have many limitations. For independent tasks, different threads can simply be started, but as soon as the completion of a task depends on another task being completed, the started tasks must be laboriously managed and coordinated. With the advent of multi-core computing, a concurrency library was therefore introduced that provides many useful abstract constructs for controlling and synchronising threads. Besides thread pools and atomic classes, these are in particular synchronisation concepts such as various locks, barriers, and semaphores. With all these concepts, parallel processes can now be implemented more easily, but a lot of manual work is still necessary.

When working with future patterns, a task is implemented in the form of a callable class whose instance is passed to a thread pool (executor) and executed asynchronously by it. The thread pool returns a future object that represents the result of the task. This proxy object can be used to access the result at a later time.

With the help of the future pattern, only one task can be executed asynchronously at a time. When the task is finished, the result must be actively read out and then the next asynchronous processing step may have to be started.

Note that the method must be thread-safe and should preferably not involve synchronisation or sequentialisation.

Due to performance considerations, especially for the calculation of splittings for TPOs, the implemented code has been heavily parallelised. For better readability of the source code, `InfOCF-Lib` has been extended by its own `Executor` class (Figure 5.1), with which the concurrent processing of individual tasks can be conveniently implemented. This encapsulation of the executor service has the goal of making the code more readable and maintainable, and also lays the foundation for parallelising `InfOCF-Lib` itself in many places with manageable effort in case it gets necessary to accelerate the library.

Fig. 5.1.: The class `Executor` in the package `util`

5.2 Total Preorders for InfOCF-Lib

As introduced in Chapter 2 the semantics of propositional logic can be extended by a preferential semantics in the form of TPOs which can be used to encode preferences or plausibility. `InfOCF-Lib` can only calculate preferential orderings from conditional knowledge bases in the form of OCFs¹⁵, but as of now has no capabilities of reading and representing externally given TPOs. This section introduces the classes and methods developed to overcome these limitations and extend `InfOCF-Lib` in such a way that it is capable of doing so.

In order to be able to develop close to the mathematical definitions and to make the code easy to understand for people familiar with TPOs, the class `Layer` (Figure 5.2) was first implemented. This class is based on the idea of TPOs as linearly ordered sets [BMW06], where each layer contains a set of interpretations. Elements can be added with the method `addElement` and all elements can be returned as a set with the method `getElements`.

Fig. 5.2.: The class `Layer` in the package `totalPreorder`

The class `TotalPreOrder` (Figure 5.3) then uses these layers to construct a TPO over possible worlds (interpretations). If the mapping of the layers does not match the number of possible interpretations over a signature, a `LayerMappingInconsistencyException` is thrown.

¹⁵`InfOCF-Lib` has many more functionalities especially in the context of conditional knowledge bases but those will not be considered in this thesis.

Fig. 5.3.: The class `TotalPreOrder` in the package `totalPreorder`

If each interpretation has been assigned to a layer, these layers are filled with the method `fillLayer` by the usage of a `TreeMap` data type for which the given integer of the layer mapping is taken as a key and the assigned interpretations (*e.g.*, the world $\bar{a}\bar{b}$ for $\Sigma = \{a, b\}$ is assigned the first key in the layer mapping) as its values. The advantage of using a `TreeMap` is that layer mappings can theoretically include “gaps”, but these are closed by the `TreeMap` due to its natural order of numbers¹⁶. Listing 5.1 shows how the method `fillLayer` is implemented.

¹⁶The `TreeMap` could in fact even be filled with string values due to the natural lexicographic order, but this will not be discussed here.

```

1 private static List<Layer<PropositionalInterpretation>> fillLayer(
    ↪ PropositionalSignature signature, int[] layerMapping) throws
    ↪ LayerMappingInconsistencyException {
2     ArrayList<PropositionalInterpretation> interpretations =
        ↪ signature.getUniverse().getInterpretations();
3     if (interpretations.size() != layerMapping.length) {
4         throw new LayerMappingInconsistencyException(
            ↪ interpretations.size(), layerMapping.length);
5     }
6
7     TreeMap<Integer, List<Integer>> mapping = new TreeMap<>();
8
9     for (int i = 0; i < layerMapping.length; i++) {
10        List<Integer> list = mapping.computeIfAbsent(
            ↪ layerMapping[i], integer -> new LinkedList<>());
11        list.add(i);
12    }
13
14    return mapping.values().stream().map(integers -> {
15        Layer<PropositionalInterpretation> layer = new Layer
            ↪ <>();
16        for (int i : integers) {
17            layer.addElement(interpretations.get(i));
18        }
19        return layer;
20    }).toList();
21 }

```

Listing 5.1: Implementation of the method `fillLayer` in the class `TotalPreOrder`. The red hooked arrows indicate linebreaks.

Example 5.1. Let $\Sigma = \{a, b\}$ be a signature, and let $lm[2, 1, 3, 2]$ be a list of integers containing the information whether one world is more plausible than another. Since `InfOCF-Lib` sorts the interpretations over a signature starting with the 0 values, the order of the integers in lm corresponds to this order, assigning the world $\bar{a}\bar{b}$ to integer 2, the world $\bar{a}b$ to integer 1, the world $a\bar{b}$ to 3, and the world ab to 2.

The method `fillLayer` now takes the first integer of lm and creates a `TreeMap` with the integer 2 as key and the associated world, *i.e.*, $\bar{a}\bar{b}$, as value.

If a key already exists, the corresponding world is simply added as a value to the existing key, thus the world ab is added to the key 2. Once the mapping is complete, a layer is constructed for each key in the `TreeMap` based on the indices created by the natural ordering of the keys, as shown in Table 5.1. Here the key

2 has the index 1 in the natural ordering, hence all values of key 2 are added to the layer with index 1. The same applies to all other keys from lm .

Tab. 5.1.: Layer mapping example with natural ordering of `TreeMap`, which yields the layer indices from which the TPO is formed.

lm	$\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$	index	\preceq
2	$\bar{a}\bar{b}, ab$	1	
1	$\bar{a}b$	0	$\bar{a}b \prec ab, \bar{a}\bar{b} \prec a\bar{b}$
3	$a\bar{b}$	2	

With the TPO object constructed from the filled layers, some methods can be called on this object. The methods `getSyntaxSplittings`, `getFinestSplitting`, and `hasSplitting` return—for the TPO under consideration, respectively—all syntax splittings, the finest syntax splitting, or a truth value whether the signatures given as parameters correspond to a syntax splitting.

The overloaded method `preferentialCompare` takes an arbitrary number of formulae and returns a TPO over the minimal worlds that these formulae satisfy, *i.e.*, according to the plausibility of the formulae. In addition, the method `generateTpoFormulas` generates the TPO over the complete conjunctions, forming the syntactic equivalent of the TPO over interpretations. With the method `toString` a method was implemented that displays the individual layers each separated by a `<` as soon as a `println` on an object of type `TotalPreOrder` is called.

Analogous to the `toString` method, the method `getTpoFormulasRepresentation` represents the TPOs in the form of complete conjunctions. Note that contrary to the method `generateTpoFormulas`, where a list of layers of propositional formulae is returned, the method `getTpoFormulasRepresentation` only returns a string representation of said TPO over the complete conjunctions. The remaining methods are helper methods whose purpose is self-explanatory.

A detailed description of how to work with the class `TotalPreOrder` can be found in the user manual extension in Appendix C.1.

5.3 TPO-Splitting for `InfOCF-Lib`

With the help of the implemented classes to represent and process TPOs via interpretations and formulae, it is now possible to implement the algorithms as in Section 4.1.

First, the column and row headers of the split-table as in Table 4.3 must be formed. For this purpose, the totality of the TPO can be used with regard to the row headers (column 1), according to which each element of a TPO must be comparable with each other. The representation of the totality is realised with the method `generateDualTpos` in the class `TpoSyntaxSplitter` (Figure 5.4), which returns a list of tuples.

Fig. 5.4.: The class `TpoSyntaxSplitter` in the package `totalPreorder`

In a second step, the marginalisation of TPOs (Definition 3.4) must be realised, which has been made possible with the class `Marginaliser` (Figure 5.5). Here, the method `generateMarginalisedTPOs` returns a list of all marginalised TPOs for the given TPO by usage of the method `generateWorlds` which basically generates the reduced worlds. Analogous to the representation of TPOs via formulae, a method is also provided here to supply developers with a string representation that makes the marginalised TPOs visible. This is achieved with the method `generateMarginalisedStringRepresentation`.

Fig. 5.5.: The class `Marginaliser` in the package `totalPreorder`

As stated in Lemma 4.1, it is sufficient to consider only the partitions of the second layer on a partition lattice for the calculation of the splittability of all Σ_i . This property is used here to design complementary marginalised TPOs with the method `partitionComplements` so that it is always clear which element contains the ω^i and which element contains the $\hat{\omega}^i$. Since working in `InfOCF-Lib` with objects of type `PropositionalVariable` is much more convenient than with `PropositionalSignature`, the work here is done on the basis of `PropositionalVariables`.

These complementary marginalised TPOs are now used, on the one hand, to determine with the method `haveEqualOmegaHat` whether two worlds of the dual TPOs (*i.e.*, each $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \Omega(\Sigma)$) have common elements, and on the other hand, to determine with the method `getOmegaI` the ω^i of two worlds, *i.e.*, the elements in which they differ, reflecting Definition 3.5, but exhaustively such that all differences are considered and not just the maximum difference.

With these preconditions now satisfied, it is possible to perform the calculations according to Algorithm 1 specified in Section 4.1 to calculate all splittable Σ_i .

Listing 5.2 shows an excerpt of the implemented code. Comments in the code are omitted here.

```

1  if (equalOmegaHat) {
2      ArrayList<PropositionalVariable> splittingCandidates = new
        ↪ ArrayList<>(omegaI.get(0).getVariables());
3      syncSplittableVariableList.put(splittingCandidates, true);
4      int omega1 = this.totalPreOrder.getLayerIndexOf(twoWorlds.first
        ↪ ());
5      int omega2 = this.totalPreOrder.getLayerIndexOf(twoWorlds.
        ↪ second());
6      int omega1i = this.totalPreOrder.getMinLayerIndexOf(omegaI.get
        ↪ (0));
7      int omega2i = this.totalPreOrder.getMinLayerIndexOf(omegaI.get
        ↪ (1));
8
9      if (!((omega1 < omega2 && omega1i < omega2i) || (omega1 >
        ↪ omega2 && omega1i > omega2i) || (omega1 == omega2 &&
        ↪ Objects.equals(omega1i, omega2i)))) {
10         syncSplittableVariableList.put(splittingCandidates, false);
11         break;
12     }
13 }

```

Listing 5.2: Excerpt from the method `getSplittableSigmaI` in the class `TpoSyntaxSplitter`. The red hooked arrows indicate linebreaks. Notice how the worlds ω_1, ω_2 as well as the worlds ω_1^i, ω_2^i are solely characterised by their layer index.

Note that the outer if-statement is part of two for-loops, reflecting the algorithm `SPLITTABLESIGMA`.

The two remaining methods `wrapTrivialSplitting` and `constructSubsignatures` are used to construct and return the trivial splitting if there is no finer splitting and to construct and return the sub-signatures from the variables.

In order to compute all splittings from the variables given by the method `getSplittableSigmaI`, these are now passed as an array, together with the size of Σ to an object of type `SubsetSumProblem` (Figure 5.6) and the method `getSubsetSumSolutions` is called on it. Here, the method `fillDpTable` is called first, with which the dp-table is filled according to Algorithm 2. Then the dp-table is traversed recursively according to Algorithm 3 to find all possible subset-sum solutions. Before these are stored in the list of splittings, they have to pass a test whether they are partitions of Σ or not.

The recursive finding of the solutions is done by the method `getSubsetSumSolution-
sRec`, while the collection of all solutions is done by the method `collectSplitting`

in which the partition check also takes place by calling the method `isPairwiseDisjoint` of the class `SetOperations` (Section 5.5). There is no need to check whether the empty set is included, as it is not considered by the class `SubsetSumProblem`. Similarly, there is no need to check whether the union of all cells of a solution results in the signature Σ , since this property is guaranteed by the subset-sum solution together with the property that the individual cells are pairwise disjoint.

Fig. 5.6.: The class `SubsetSumProblem` in the package `util`

Listings 5.3 and 5.4 show the filling of dp-table and the four cases of the method `getSubsetSumSolutionsRec` which find all subset-sum solutions recursively.

```

1  dpTable = new boolean[splittableSigmaIArrayLength][
    ↪ superSignatureSize + 1];
2  for (int i = 0; i < splittableSigmaIArrayLength; ++i) {
3      dpTable[i][0] = true;
4  }
5
6  if (splittableSigmaIArray[0].size() < superSignatureSize) {
7      dpTable[0][splittableSigmaIArray[0].size()] = true;
8  }
9
10 for (int i = 1; i < splittableSigmaIArrayLength; ++i) {
11     for (int j = 0; j < superSignatureSize + 1; ++j) {
12         dpTable[i][j] = (splittableSigmaIArray[i].size() <= j) ? (
    ↪ dpTable[i - 1][j] || dpTable[i - 1][j -
    ↪ splittableSigmaIArray[i].size()]) : dpTable[i - 1][j
    ↪ ];
13     }
14 }
  
```

Listing 5.3: Filling of the dp-table in the method `fillDpTable` of the class `SubsetSumProblem`. The red hooked arrows indicate linebreaks.

```

1  if (splittableSigmaIArrayLength == 0 && superSignatureSize != 0 &&
    ↪ dpTable[0][superSignatureSize]) {
2  currentSolution.add(splittableSigmaIArray[
    ↪ splittableSigmaIArrayLength]);
3  collectSplitting(listOfSplittings, currentSolution);
4
5  return;
6  }
7
8  if (splittableSigmaIArrayLength == 0 && superSignatureSize == 0) {
9  collectSplitting(listOfSplittings, currentSolution);
10
11 return;
12 }
13
14 if (dpTable[splittableSigmaIArrayLength - 1][superSignatureSize]) {
15 ArrayList<ArrayList<T>> solutionRec = new ArrayList<>(
    ↪ currentSolution);
16 getSubsetSumSolutionsRec(listOfSplittings, splittableSigmaIArray,
    ↪ splittableSigmaIArrayLength - 1, superSignatureSize,
    ↪ solutionRec);
17 }
18
19 if (superSignatureSize >= splittableSigmaIArray[
    ↪ splittableSigmaIArrayLength].size() && dpTable[
    ↪ splittableSigmaIArrayLength - 1][superSignatureSize -
    ↪ splittableSigmaIArray[splittableSigmaIArrayLength].size()]) {
20 currentSolution.add(splittableSigmaIArray[
    ↪ splittableSigmaIArrayLength]);
21 getSubsetSumSolutionsRec(listOfSplittings, splittableSigmaIArray,
    ↪ splittableSigmaIArrayLength - 1, superSignatureSize -
    ↪ splittableSigmaIArray[splittableSigmaIArrayLength].size(),
    ↪ currentSolution);
22 }

```

Listing 5.4: If-statements for the recursive traversal to find all subset-sum solutions in the method `getSubestSumSolutionsRec` of the class `SubsetSumProblem`. The red hooked arrows indicate linebreaks.

A detailed description of how to work with the class `TpoSyntaxSplitter` can be found in the user manual extension in Appendix C.2.1.

5.4 \mathcal{R} -Splitting for InfOCF-Lib

Contrary to the extensions needed to perform syntax splitting for TPOs in InfOCF-Lib, enabling it to perform syntax splitting on conditional knowledge bases can be realised with only one new class. The main methods to split the syntax of a conditional knowledge base in the class `RSplitter` (Figure 5.7) are the methods `getApplicants`, `splitSyntax`, and `refineApplicants`. The method `getApplicants` basically takes the variables of each conditional and puts them in a set of sets which represents the applicants of the given conditional knowledge base. The method `splitSyntax` takes those applicants and calls `refineApplicants` while the sum of the cardinalities of all applicants is greater than the cardinality of variables used in \mathcal{R} . The first step of the method `refineApplicants` takes the set of applicants and removes all strict subsets of its subsets. In a second step it combines all subsets which have non-empty intersections.

Fig. 5.7.: The class `RSplitter` in the package `conditionalLogic`

The whole process of getting the variables in \mathcal{R} as well as the refinement of the applicants and the removal of strict subsets is heavily parallelised due to performance considerations. However, this parallelisation comes with an overhead such that a performance increase can not be expected for small signatures.

The unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting will be returned in the form of a set containing disjoint sub-signatures of Σ or with just Σ in the case of only the trivial splitting being possible.

An \mathcal{R} -splitting $\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$ usually is accompanied by its partitioned conditional knowledge base $\{\mathcal{R}_1, \dots, \mathcal{R}_n\}$, which is why the additional method `getSubKBs` has

been added to the class. This method returns the conditional knowledge sub-bases that can be formed over the corresponding sub-signatures and the conditionals of the corresponding conditional knowledge base.

The method `getApplicants` initialises the set $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ by simply taking the variables contained in each conditional and putting them into one set per conditional. As this process becomes more complex with each additional conditional $r \in \mathcal{R}$, it is parallelised by assigning a task to each conditional. Since the sets of $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ do not depend on each other, no *race conditions* can arise and parallelisation can easily be implemented.

The method `splitSyntax` coincides with Algorithm 5 SPLITKB from Section 4.2 and calls `refineApplicants` as long as the cardinality of all variables in $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ does not match the size of variables used in \mathcal{R} . As soon as those two match, the variables not contained in \mathcal{R} are added in accordance with Corollary 3.2. At last, the sub-signatures are being constructed in distinct tasks from the variables now split, yielding the desired result.

```

1  Set<Set<PropositionalVariable>> inputSet = new HashSet<>(List.
    ↪ copyOf(this.applicants));
2  Set<Set<PropositionalVariable>> resultSet;
3
4  int rSize = flattenVariablesOfR().size();
5  int resultSize;
6
7  do {
8      resultSet = refineApplicants(inputSet);
9      resultSize = applicantsCardinality(resultSet);
10
11     if (resultSize < rSize) {
12         throw new RuntimeException("applicants Cardinality is lower
    ↪ than Variables of R size.");
13     }
14 } while (resultSize > rSize);
15 resultSet.addAll(getRemainderVariablesOfSignature());

```

Listing 5.5: Excerpt from the method `splitSyntax` in the class `RSplitter`. The red hooked arrows indicate linebreaks.

In the first step of the method `refineApplicants`, which mirrors parts of Algorithm 4 FINDPATHRELEVANCE from Section 4.2, the `removeSubsets` method from the class `SetOperations` (Section 5.5) is called to remove all strict subsets in $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$. Since this method comes with certain challenges, such as *deadlock prevention* due to heavy parallelisation, a *read write lock* is implemented. The next step is to check

for all subsets of $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ whether some of them (two are checked each time) have non-empty intersections, and if so, the first of them becomes the union of the two, while the second is removed. Each check is performed in an assigned task, and the read and write lock ensures that no deadlock situation occurs. When working with an array data structure, removal is achieved by tagging the sets to be excluded with the value `null` and ignoring them in further steps, which makes it much easier to handle. The last step *invokes* all tasks to complete the calculation.

The overall straightforward implementation of an eliminator of strict subsets of sets in $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$, namely the method `removeSubsets`, is parallelised in a similar fashion as the above `refineApplicants`.

With the sub-signatures constructed by `splitSyntax`, the conditional knowledge sub-bases can easily be constructed over the split syntax as well which the method `getSubKBs` achieves. The constructed knowledge sub-bases can then be used by `InfOCF-Lib` as usual.

The rest of the methods are helper methods to ease readability of the code. The method `applicantsCardinality` returns the cardinality of all elements in the set $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$, *i.e.*, each variable is counted every time it occurs and does not care about duplicates which is used as the termination condition for `splitSyntax`. Those methods serve the purpose of realising the concept of Corollary 3.2 and Lemma 4.3. Here the method `flattenVariablesOfR` gets $\Sigma(\mathcal{R})$ and the method `notContainedInAnyConditional` subtracts it from Σ , *i.e.*, gets $\Sigma \setminus \Sigma(\mathcal{R})$. Finally the method `getRemainderVariablesOfSignature` takes those variables in $\Sigma \setminus \Sigma(\mathcal{R})$ and puts each of them in a singleton set which will be added to the refined applicants.

Listing 5.6 shows an excerpt of the method `refineApplicants`.

```
1  // for every element in array create a task that compares the
   ↪ element with the remaining elements
2  for (int i = 0; i < applicants.length; i++) {
3      final int finalI = i;
4      tasks.add(() -> {
5          for (int j = finalI + 1; j < applicants.length; j++) {
6              // do not read when another thread wants to modify data
7              rwLock.readLock().lock();
8              Set<PropositionalVariable> applI = applicants[finalI];
9              Set<PropositionalVariable> applJ = applicants[j];
10             rwLock.readLock().unlock();
11             // ignore pairs with null values -> are already
               ↪ simplified/checked
12             if (applI == null || applJ == null) {
13                 continue;
14             }
15             if (SetOperations.haveIntersection(applI, applJ)) {
16                 // request exclusive access when modifying data
17                 rwLock.writeLock().lock();
18                 // reread data to check for modification
19                 applI = applicants[finalI];
20                 applJ = applicants[j];
21                 // if one of the sets is null it was already
                   ↪ checked
22                 if (applI != null && applJ != null) {
23                     // combine and delete other
24                     applI.addAll(applJ);
25                     applicants[j] = null;
26                 }
27                 rwLock.writeLock().unlock();
28             }
29         }
30         return null;
31     });
32 }
33 // start all tasks and wait for completion
34 Executor.waitForAll(tasks);
35 return Arrays.stream(applicants).filter(Objects::nonNull).collect(
   ↪ Collectors.toSet());
```

Listing 5.6: Excerpt from the method `refineApplicants` in the class `RSplitter`. The red hooked arrows indicate linebreaks.

A detailed description of how to work with the class `RSplitter` can be found in the user manual extension in Appendix C.2.2.

The class `ConditionalKnowledgeBase` (Figure 5.8) has been extended with the two methods `getSyntaxSplitting` and `getSplitKbs` which return the \mathcal{R} -splitting and the knowledge sub-bases for the corresponding \mathcal{R} -splitting, respectively.

Fig. 5.8.: The class `ConditionalKnowledgeBase` in the package `conditionalLogic`

5.5 Additional Classes

For the realisation of either the calculation of TPO-splittings or the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting, some methods could be used for both problems and are also very generically applicable for other application purposes. To abstract from the specific problems solved here, some methods have therefore been moved to the `util` package. The classes `SubsetSumProblem` and `Executor` are also in this package.

The class most frequently used in the implementation and its methods is the class `SetOperations` (Figure 5.9), which represents two classic set operations with the newly implemented methods `haveIntersection` and `removeSubsets` as well as the method `isPairwiseDisjoint`. Here, the method `haveIntersection` only returns a truth value indicating whether two sets have a common intersection or not, whereas the method `removeSubsets` removes strict subsets in a set of subsets and the method `isPairwiseDisjoint` returns, as the name indicates, whether a given set of sets is pairwise distinct, which is sufficient in the case of assuring if a subset-sum solution is a partition of Σ .

The rest of the methods in this class belongs natively to `InfOCF-Lib`. All these methods were previously in the class `Powerset`, but were integrated into the class `SetOperations` together with the new methods as part of this work.

Fig. 5.9.: The class `SetOperations` in the package `util`

The class `Tuple` (Figure 5.10), with the help of which many parts of the TPO-splitting could be realised, proved to be very helpful. For example, this class was used to map the ω^i to their corresponding $\hat{\omega}^i$.

Fig. 5.10.: The class `Tuple` in the package `util`

For a more generic use of syntax splittings in `InfOCF-Lib` the class `SyntaxSplittingFactory` (Figure 5.11) has been implemented which allows for the convenient usage of syntax splittings for various frameworks (TPOs and conditional knowledge bases) through the interfaces `Splittable` and `SyntaxSplitter` and can be extended in a straightforward fashion.

Fig. 5.11.: The package `syntaxSplitting` with the class `SyntaxSplittingFactory` and the interfaces `SyntaxSplitter` and `Splittable`

Analogous to the already existing knowledge base parser in `InfOCF-Lib`, an additional parser was implemented that allows to read TPOs from `.cl`-files. For this purpose, the class `ConditionalKnowledgeBaseParser` in the package `text.parsing` was first generalised such that the inherent signature parser could be moved to its own abstract class. Based on this, it was possible to write the class `TpoParser` (Figure 5.12) that only has to read a signature accompanied by an integer array instead of a conditional knowledge base.

Fig. 5.12.: The class `TpoParser` in the package `text.parsing`

Evaluation of the Implemented Algorithms

To evaluate the implemented algorithms, worst case scenarios must first be defined. Such scenarios can be constructed in a relatively straightforward way in the context of TPOs, since the worst case occurs exactly, when all $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ are splittable so that the complete split-table must be calculated. This immediately results in the worst case for the second part of the calculation of TPO-splittings, namely the construction of the individual syntax splittings from the possible subset-sum solutions. In contrast, in the context of \mathcal{R} -splittings a worst case cannot be simulated so easily, it can only be stated that the complexity increases with increasing cardinality of both Σ and \mathcal{R} as well as with increasing size of the conditionals $r \in \mathcal{R}$.

During the work on this thesis, it was soon decided that the algorithms to be implemented should, as far as possible and reasonable, be implemented by means of parallel programming in order to benefit from the advantages of modern multi-core processors. Given that the runtime of concurrently executed programs strongly depends on the hardware provided, it is important to know the respective specifications of the hardware with which the runtime measurements were carried out. In this case, this was done with a Schenker Slim15 laptop (16-inch, 2019) with an Intel i7-8565U CPU at 1.80GHz and 16GB of DDR4 RAM at 2,400 MHz. The laptop runs on an Arch Linux operating system with the Linux 5.18.9-arch1-1 kernel. Development has been done with Java openjdk 16.0.2 and IntelliJ IDEA 2022.1 at the latest.

In order to measure the runtime performance with as little statistical noise as possible, 10,000,000 iterations were performed for the calculation of TPO-splittings with $|\Sigma| = 2$ and all acquired measurements were averaged. For this purpose, Java `System.nanoTime` was used, with microseconds as the unit of comparison. Due to the exponentially increasing runtime complexity by a factor of 7–13 with parallelisation and 9–14 without parallelisation (see Table B.1 in Appendix B) with each additional variable in Σ , the number of iterations was reduced by a factor of 10 per $|\Sigma| + 1$, which led to the fact that with $|\Sigma| = 8$ the measurements were carried out with only 10 iterations. Considering that each iteration requires 6.75 minutes (with concurrent processing) to calculate the TPO-splittings of a signature

with $|\Sigma| = 8$ on the available hardware, the variance of a few milliseconds was negligible.

The runtime complexity which is exponentially increasing can be visualised clearly on a logarithmic scale, illustrated in Figure 6.1.

Fig. 6.1.: Scaling of time consumption of TPO-splitting calculation per $|\Sigma|$ (log)

Measuring the runtime of the computation of unique finest \mathcal{R} -splittings was done continuously at 100,000 iterations, since the computation time increased in a very manageable range when either $|\Sigma|$ or $|\mathcal{R}|$ or both were increased.

Determining at which sizes of either $|\Sigma|$ or $|\mathcal{R}|$ for both frameworks it was beneficial to use parallelisation, the implementation was adapted to work without parallelisation. To determine the overhead that is produced by the parallelisation process, the executor service presented in Section 5.1 was adapted to use only one thread by using `Executors.newSingleThreadExecutor` instead of `Executors.newWorkStealingPool`, which simulates sequential processing of the computations. Since this preserves the overhead caused by parallelisation, an impression can be gained of how much it affects the calculation at all. Given the high complexity of TPO-splittings however, this plays a minor role early on as can be seen in Table B.2 in Appendix B. This observation cannot be made for the calculation of the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting. Here the overhead is clearly noticeable (see Table B.3 in Appendix B) which is reflected in the more tentative acceleration using parallelisation.

Therefore, in the following, some measurements are presented to give an idea of what orders of magnitude of $|\Sigma|$ for TPO-splittings as well as $|\Sigma|$ and $|\mathcal{R}|$ for \mathcal{R} -splittings are within the realm of feasibility for acceptable runtimes.

Evaluation of Automated Calculation of TPO-splittings

Simulating worst case scenarios where all $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ are splittable can easily be done by putting all worlds $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$ in the same layer, *i.e.*, by using *uniform total preorders* [KIBB20] for different sizes of Σ . Signatures with a size of 1 were not considered in the evaluation, since, due to the implementation, these are only returned as the trivial splitting without any calculations being performed.

The main observation, as can be seen in Table 6.1, is that parallelisation proves to be beneficial from the start and increases the computation speed up to a factor of 4 compared to sequential processing.

Tab. 6.1.: Sizes of Σ and the corresponding runtime with either sequential or concurrent processing. The measurements were taken in nanoseconds but are presented here in microseconds for brevity.

$ \Sigma $	Average speed sequential	Average speed concurrent	Speedup factor (seq./con.)
2	493.03 μs	336.97 μs	1.46
3	4,705.03 μs	2,585.58 μs	1.82
4	56,088.84 μs	18,565.24 μs	3.02
5	792,821.37 μs	251,496.11 μs	3.15
6	10,161,737.98 μs	2,545,524.98 μs	3.99
7	131,317,970.19 μs	31,984,373.29 μs	4.11
8	1,561,621,082.80 μs	405,597,449.00 μs	3.85

An interesting observation is that while the method `getSplittableSigmaI` performs most of the calculation steps with the expected speed, within these calculation steps the calculation of the splittability of each $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ takes about two thirds and the preceding method `generateDualTpos` takes about one third of the time. At this point, development could begin to optimise the implemented algorithms so that the generation of the dual TPOs works faster.

However, due to the totality of TPOs, each world must be compared with each other, which corresponds to a complexity of the sum of all numbers from 1 to $|\Omega(\Sigma)| - 1$. This calculation can be expressed, slightly modified, with the Gaussian sum formula: $\sum_{i=1}^{|\Omega(\Sigma)|-1} i = \frac{|\Omega(\Sigma)|(|\Omega(\Sigma)|-1)}{2} = \frac{2^{|\Sigma|}(2^{|\Sigma|}-1)}{2}$. Accordingly, this formula can also be used to calculate the number of rows of the split-table, while the number of columns corresponds to the stirling subset numbers [Twe03; Knu92] with $k = 2$, which can be expressed by Euler's formula for stirling numbers [QG15] $\left\{ \begin{matrix} |\Sigma| \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{i=0}^k (-1)^i \binom{k}{i} (k-i)^{|\Sigma|}$. However, this formula gives the number of k -subsets of Σ in general and not the number of all $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$, though according to

Lemma 4.1 the number calculated here with $k = 2$ merely needs to be doubled, resulting in the number of all $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$.

With k fixed at 2, the resulting formula can be greatly simplified, giving a much less complex way to calculate the number of all 2-element partitions which can be thought of partitioning n elements in two distinct compartments. Not concerning the empty set, there would be 2^n distributions, yet since 2 of these contain the empty set, these two must be subtracted. Considering that the initial goal would be to count the number of ways the set of n elements can be partitioned in two ways, the possible $2^n - 2$ distributions must be divided by 2, thus yielding $\binom{n}{2} = \frac{2^n - 2}{2}$. According to Lemma 4.1¹⁷, this formula can now be used to calculate the number of all $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ conveniently: $2 \cdot \binom{|\Sigma|}{2} = 2^{|\Sigma|} - 2$.

Evaluation of Automated Calculation of the Unique Finest \mathcal{R} -splitting

As mentioned above, it is not as easy to simulate worst cases for the calculation of unique finest syntax splittings of conditional knowledge bases as it is for TPOs, since the calculation is already very fast here naturally. Additionally, there are a lot of dependencies which might have an effect on the efficiency of the implementation, such that it is not always clear when an alteration of \mathcal{R} worsens the overall speed of the implementation. However, in order to get an impression of when parallelisation also has a positive effect here, three scenarios have been constructed. In the first scenario, a conditional knowledge base with $|\Sigma| = 7$ and $|\mathcal{R}| \in \{4, \dots, 8\}$ is considered and in the second scenario a knowledge base with $|\Sigma| = 14$ and $|\mathcal{R}| \in \{11, \dots, 20\}$. The third scenario considered a knowledge base with $|\Sigma| = 56$ and $|\mathcal{R}| \in \{20, 40, 80, 160, 240, 320\}$. Note that the incrementally added conditionals were chosen randomly and not according to a specific selective procedure, except for the signature of size 56. Here there have been up to 80 distinct conditionals which have been simply multiplied for the sole purpose of adding workload to the implementation.

The results of Table 6.2 show that for knowledge bases with $|\Sigma| \approx 10$ and $|\mathcal{R}| \approx 15$ there is hardly any speedup due to parallelisation. Tendencies can be recognised, but these are contradicted by other results, as can be seen from the non-monotonic course of the speedup factor. However, parallelisation seems to have a positive effect at $|\Sigma| = 56$ and $|\mathcal{R}| = 80$ at the latest. Interestingly, even at $|\Sigma| = 14$ and

¹⁷This formula can in fact even be constructed without the use of Lemma 4.1 by taking the cardinality of the powerset $\mathcal{P}(\Sigma)$ minus Σ and the empty set, yielding the same formula: $|\mathcal{P}(\Sigma)| - 2 = 2^{|\Sigma|} - 2$. However, the present implementation uses the property of all Σ_i being contained in the second layer of the corresponding partition lattice and as such complies more with the notion of stirlings subset numbers.

$|\mathcal{R}| \in \{17, \dots, 20\}$ there seems to be a continuous runtime acceleration resulting in a speedup factor of 1.7–1.9.

Tab. 6.2.: Sizes of Σ and \mathcal{R} the corresponding runtime with either sequential or concurrent processing. The measurements are presented in microseconds here.

$\frac{ \Sigma }{ \mathcal{R} }$	Average speed sequential	Average speed concurrent	Speedup factor (seq./con.)
7/4	58.77 μs	77.80 μs	0.76
7/5	59.99 μs	79.03 μs	0.76
7/6	58.68 μs	73.94 μs	0.79
7/7	73.81 μs	80.11 μs	0.92
7/8	82.86 μs	68.62 μs	1.21
14/11	85.03 μs	83.29 μs	1.02
14/12	111.57 μs	123.61 μs	0.90
14/13	96.09 μs	97.08 μs	0.99
14/14	85.71 μs	91.28 μs	0.94
14/15	161.90 μs	88.81 μs	1.82
14/16	80.26 μs	87.40 μs	0.92
14/17	180.59 μs	91.30 μs	1.98
14/18	168.97 μs	98.07 μs	1.72
14/19	177.75 μs	102.39 μs	1.74
14/20	195.19 μs	102.25 μs	1.91
56/20	12,120.29 μs	14,780.84 μs	0.82
56/40	39,625.77 μs	36,355.35 μs	1.09
56/80	258,025.02 μs	203,280.58 μs	1.27
56/160	134,636.52 μs	111,143.83 μs	1.21
56/240	238,897.04 μs	178,577.54 μs	1.34
56/320	198,905.91 μs	110,095.17 μs	1.81

It is further interesting that the computation time has a large variance, showing that it does not necessarily increase from smaller to larger knowledge bases. This can be seen well here at $|\Sigma| = 14$ and $|\mathcal{R}| \in \{15, 16\}$, where, inspite of the additional workload, the calculation time is halved. At the same time, the parallel processing remains almost constant for the same signature and $|\mathcal{R}| \in \{14, \dots, 17\}$.

Another observation made during the measurements was that with $|\Sigma| = 56$ and $|\mathcal{R}| = 80$ all cores had a load of 19–22%, indicating that larger knowledge bases would be needed to simulate a worst case. However, with the same signature but a conditional knowledge base of size 320, all cores were still mostly below 30% which indicates even much larger knowledge bases are required to benefit fully from the parallelisation when 4 cores can be utilised. A case supporting this observation could even be simulated using the `Executors.newFixedThreadPool` with two specified cores. Here, the workload of the two cores was constant at 100% and the computation time could be halved with a speed-up factor of 2.11 for $|\Sigma| = 56$ and $|\mathcal{R}| = 320$ compared to using the `Executors.newWorkStealingPool` (see Table B.4 in Appendix B).

Within the method `splitSyntax` further statistics can be surveyed, according to which the initialisation of `appl(\mathcal{R})` takes $\approx 4\%$ of the runtime, the computation of the variables not contained in the conditionals takes $\approx 6\%$ and the refinement of `appl(\mathcal{R})` takes $\approx 89\%$. However, these values depend strongly on the conditional knowledge base, since, for example, the proportion used for the computation of variables not included in \mathcal{R} increases with each variable not included, or converges to 0 provided that all variables are included in some conditional $r \in \mathcal{R}$.

Final Remarks

In the preceding chapters, necessary formalities were introduced to realise syntax splitting automatically for the frameworks of TPOs and conditional knowledge bases. Later, algorithms were introduced to realise this automation, which were implemented and evaluated afterwards. This chapter now discusses limitations of computation time, problems with the realism of \mathcal{R} -splittings and addresses problems of TPO-splittings in the context of belief change. In addition, possible extensions of `InfOCF-Lib` are explained, and possible further research on syntax splitting is addressed.

7.1 Discussion

Runtime complexity To overcome the high combinatorial complexity, or to contain it somewhat, the implemented code was largely parallelised. This parallelisation comes with a certain overhead, which means that no runtime reductions are to be expected for small $|\Sigma|$. However, this only holds for \mathcal{R} -splittings and machines with a large number of cores, for which this overhead can have a strong detrimental effect. As for TPO-splittings, the overhead plays a minor role from the start, since the complexity increases strongly in a very short time. The number of possible interpretations—of which all must be considered—is subject to exponential growth with $2^{|\Sigma|}$. As shown in Chapter 6, the number of rows and columns for the split-table such as Table 4.3 can be easily calculated, where the number of rows corresponds to $\frac{2^{|\Sigma|}(2^{|\Sigma|}-1)}{2}$ and the number of columns corresponds to $2^{|\Sigma|} - 2$.

The concurrent calculation of all TPO-splittings for a given TPO can here be shortened by up to 75% in contrast to the sequential calculation. Due to the high complexity with which the calculation time increases by a factor of approximately 11 with each additional variable in Σ , the computation of all TPO-splittings for a signature with $|\Sigma| = 14$ would result in a calculation time of roughly 18 years in the worst case with the hardware used here.

Absurdly, the worst case in terms of runtime complexity occurs when every partition is a splitting, yielding the most possibilities to reduce complexity by means of syntax

splitting, whereas the algorithm terminates fastest when counterexamples are found early on that deny the splittability of all Σ_i . However, since the worst case occurs when for example all worlds are contained in the same layer, the conclusion can be drawn early that all splittings are possible and the maximally fine splitting is indeed the unique finest splitting. With the knowledge of the present TPO being a uniform TPO, no calculation is needed and the worst case collapses into a trivial case. Given that the research of syntax splittings for TPOs is still very young, further exploration here may possibly lead to additional structural constellations from which early termination conditions can be derived that determine splittings without the need to check all $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma$ for their splittability.

As can be seen in Chapter 6, runtime complexity does not play a major role for \mathcal{R} -splittings as long as $|\Sigma|$ and $|\mathcal{R}|$ are relatively small. Nonetheless, a performance advantage can already be observed from a size of $|\Sigma| = 56$ and $|\mathcal{R}| = 80$, even if the general calculation still takes place in fairly moderate times.

Challenges with \mathcal{R} -splitting and real world As Figure 3.2c shows, modelling the real world with conditional knowledge bases can lead to situations where syntax can no longer be split (*e.g.*, penguins can also swim and it would be irrational to deny them the ability to swim). At the same time, certain characteristics that definitely do not apply to an object could be modelled with the negation of said characteristic. A relation with a conditional of the form $(\bar{a}|b)$ leads to a dependency between the letters a and b although a might not at all be relevant for the situation itself, if, for example, it holds for b that it exactly does not have the characteristic a .

That conditional knowledge bases are often fully connected in reality and thus the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting corresponds to the signature Σ was also already established by Wilhelm and Kern-Isberner in [WK21]. Despite the tactile fact that penguins can swim, an inference that eels can swim should be possible to be drawn without this inference depending on knowledge about penguins and their property of being non-flying birds.

Wilhelm and Kern-Isberner introduce the concept of focused inference and its generalisation of iterated focused inference. Here, a knowledge base is not separated according to whether sub-bases can be expressed by partial signatures that are irrelevant to each other, *i.e.*, epistemically irrelevant. Instead, the knowledge base is focussed to the extent that it is capable of answering a query and drawing inferences based on a subset of the underlying knowledge base.

Belief change and TPO-splitting As stated in [KIB17], from a split TPO whose marginalised TPOs have undergone revision, the revised TPO without splitting cannot be reconstructed, since TPOs provide a purely qualitative environment. The postulates (MR) and (P^{it}) presented by Kern-Isberner and Brewka do not imply each other. Therefore, the fundamental question is how useful it is to tear apart epistemic states represented by TPOs by means of syntax splitting if they cannot be reassembled. Nevertheless, at least the knowledge of possible splittings should be helpful, so that TPO-splittings do not have to be carried out, but calculated, such that the knowledge of the relevant parts is present.

7.2 Further Development

As research about knowledge representation and reasoning does not rest, there are also constantly new concepts that can possibly be implemented in `InfOCF-Lib`. This section is intended to give an insight into what can be integrated in principle and what concerns current research in particular. A theoretical aspect is also addressed.

Extensions Regarding Inference

For example, the possibility to draw inferences based on a TPO, analogous to the already existing possibility of `InfOCF-Lib` to infer with the help of OCFs, would be conceivable.

Analogously it would be interesting to integrate inference with the recently introduced system W [KB22], presumably a good addition to the included possibilities for drawing inferences with system P [KLM90], system Z [Pea90], and c -representations [BEKI16; Bei+18]. Further, as stated in [HB22a], system W complies with syntax splitting.

Another interesting approach might as well be an implementation of the focused inference mentioned above to compensate for the weaknesses of the \mathcal{R} -splitting.

Extensions Regarding Syntax Splitting

As already discussed in Chapter 5, there are other frameworks besides TPOs that can be used to represent epistemic states, although `InfOCF-Lib` uses OCFs for this so far. Syntax splitting can be performed on these OCFs, which is also explained in detail in [KIB17].

An OCF maps an ordinal to each propositional formula of an agent, inducing a TPO. The smaller the ordinal, the more plausible the formula. Or the other way around: the higher the ordinal, the more surprising the formula.

In [KIB17], Kern-Isberner and Brewka define an OCF κ as a function $\kappa : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{N}_0 \cup \{\infty\}$ that maps each world to a natural number with $\kappa^{-1}(0) \neq \emptyset$ ensuring at least one world to be assigned the rank 0. The rank of a formula A is $\kappa(A) = \min_{\omega \in \text{Mod}(A)} \kappa(\omega)$. A formula A is believed if $\kappa(\bar{A}) > 0$ (which implies particularly $\kappa(A) = 0$) [KIB17].

Directly from this the belief set for an OCF κ can be extracted, *i.e.*, $\text{Bel}(\kappa) = \mathcal{T}(\{\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma) \mid \kappa(\omega) = 0\})$. Inducing a TPO \preceq_κ , a world ω_1 is more plausible than a world ω_2 *iff* the assigned rank of world ω_1 given by the OCF is lower than the rank of world ω_2 , *i.e.*, $\omega_1 \preceq_\kappa \omega_2$ *iff* $\kappa(\omega_1) \leq_\kappa \kappa(\omega_2)$ ¹⁸ for worlds $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \Omega$.

Example 7.1. Consider Example 2.3 with $\Sigma_{abc} = \{a, b, c\}$ and TPO \preceq_{abc} . A ranking function κ_{abc} maintaining the same plausibility order as \preceq_{abc} could look like the one in Table 7.1:

Tab. 7.1.: Ranking function κ_{abc}

ω	κ	ω	κ
abc	3	$\bar{a}bc$	4
$ab\bar{c}$	1	$\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	3
$a\bar{b}c$	4	$\bar{a}\bar{b}c$	2
$\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	3	$\bar{a}\bar{b}c$	0

Note that world $\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$ has the rank 0 and is therefore, analogously to the minimal world in Example 2.3, the world in which the formulae of the belief set can be expressed.

Degrees of plausibility can also be assigned to conditionals by setting $\kappa(B|A) = \kappa(AB) - \kappa(A)$. A conditional $(B|A)$ is accepted in the epistemic state represented by κ , written as $\kappa \models (B|A)$, *iff* $\kappa(AB) < \kappa(A\bar{B})$, *i.e.*, *iff* AB is more plausible than $A\bar{B}$. Accordingly, a conditional knowledge base \mathcal{R} is accepted by an epistemic state κ if κ accepts all conditionals of \mathcal{R} . Similar to Example 2.4, the conditional $(\bar{c}|\bar{a}\bar{b})$ is accepted by κ_{abc} but the conditional $(c|ab)$ is not, *i.e.*, $\kappa_{abc} \models (\bar{c}|\bar{a}\bar{b})$ but $\kappa_{abc} \not\models (c|ab)$, because $\kappa_{abc}(\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}) < \kappa_{abc}(\bar{a}\bar{b}c)$ but $\kappa_{abc}(abc) \not< \kappa_{abc}(ab\bar{c})$.

In [KIB17], Kern-Isberner and Brewka provide definitions of how to perform syntax splitting on OCFs too, where they state that an OCF κ splits over Σ whenever κ can be constructed from its marginals κ_i with respect to the corresponding Σ_i .

¹⁸Note that the relationship between ω_1 and ω_2 must be the same as $\kappa(\omega_1)$ and $\kappa(\omega_2)$ and vice versa, *i.e.*, $\omega_1 \prec \omega_2$ *iff* $\kappa(\omega_1) < \kappa(\omega_2)$ and $\omega_1 \sim \omega_2$ *iff* $\kappa(\omega_1) = \kappa(\omega_2)$.

Definition 7.1 (Syntax Splitting for OCFs [KIB17]). Let $\{\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_n\}$ be a partition of Σ , and let κ be an OCF defined on $\Omega(\Sigma)$. $\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$ is a syntax splitting for the OCF κ iff there are OCFs κ_i defined on Σ_i with $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that

$$\kappa(\omega) = \kappa(\omega^1 \dots \omega^n) = \kappa_1(\omega^1) + \dots + \kappa_n(\omega^n)$$

holds for all $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$.

This is written as $\kappa = \kappa_1 \oplus \dots \oplus \kappa_n$ and in this case, $\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$ will be called *OCF-splitting*.

As part of the notion of OCF-splitting, they also provide a proposition that if an OCF κ has an OCF-splitting, then its induced TPO has the same splitting.

Proposition 7.1 ([KIB17]). If $\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$ is an OCF-splitting for κ , then $\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$ is a TPO-splitting for \preceq_κ .

With `InfOCF-Lib`, there is already the possibility to compute OCFs from conditional knowledge bases. In the context of this work, a further functionality was implemented with which the induced TPO can be obtained from a given OCF. For this purpose, the class `RankingFunction` (Figure 7.1) was extended by the method `getOcfInducedTpo`, which fills the integer array with the calculated ranks and constructs a TPO over the given signature and the filled integer array. Empty ranks are simply deleted by the class `TotalPreOrder`, leaving only the qualitative information of plausibility. As this induced TPO is of the type `TotalPreOrder`, all the above mentioned methods concerning TPOs can be applied.

Fig. 7.1.: The class `RankingFunction` in the package `ocf`

However, this of course does not yet provide any functionality with which OCF-splittings can be calculated, but only splittings for the induced TPO. Nevertheless, if considering the structure of an OCF-splitting, certain similarities with regard to the solution of the TPO-splitting can be observed. For example, an OCF-splitting can be considered and solved as a subset-sum problem, for which basic functionalities are already available and which have been implemented generically to such an extent that they can be applied to other problems with relatively little effort.

Note that the OCF in Example 7.1 does not have an OCF-splitting, yet its induced TPO does have the splitting $\{a, b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$. However, if the OCF gets altered slightly, it does have an OCF-splitting while the induced TPO—due to the qualitative information of the worlds $\bar{a}bc$ and $a\bar{b}c$ being the least plausible worlds—stays the same.

Example 7.2. Consider Example 2.3 again. Another ranking function κ'_{abc} maintaining the same qualitative information about plausibility between worlds can look like the one in Table 7.2.

Tab. 7.2.: Ranking function κ'_{abc}

ω	κ'	ω	κ'
abc	3	$\bar{a}bc$	5
$ab\bar{c}$	1	$\bar{a}b\bar{c}$	3
$a\bar{b}c$	5	$\bar{a}\bar{b}c$	2
$a\bar{b}\bar{c}$	3	$\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	0

According to Definition 7.1, if the marginalised ranks κ_i of κ sum to κ , then $\Sigma_1 \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} \Sigma_n$ is an OCF-splitting, which is the case for $\kappa'_{abc} = \kappa'^{\Sigma_1}_{abc} \oplus \kappa'^{\Sigma_2}_{abc}$ with $\Sigma_1 = \{a, b\}$ and $\Sigma_2 = \{c\}$.

Simply put, an OCF thus has an OCF-splitting exactly when it results from the sum of its marginals over a certain reduced signature for all $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$. Conversely, this could be used to calculate which ranks $\kappa(\omega)$ for all $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma)$ can be calculated from the sum of all partitioned ranks of Σ to infer all OCF splittings. To elaborate this naive approach let the sub-signatures $\Sigma_i \subset \Sigma_{abc}$ with $i \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$ be $\Sigma_1 = \{a\}$, $\Sigma_2 = \{b\}$, $\Sigma_3 = \{c\}$, $\Sigma_4 = \{a, b\}$, $\Sigma_5 = \{a, c\}$, and $\Sigma_6 = \{b, c\}$, and let Σ_{abc} be partitioned as follows: $\mathcal{P}_1 = \{\Sigma_4, \Sigma_3\}$, $\mathcal{P}_2 = \{\Sigma_5, \Sigma_2\}$, $\mathcal{P}_3 = \{\Sigma_6, \Sigma_1\}$, and $\mathcal{P}_4 = \{\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2, \Sigma_3\}$. Table 7.3 provides the marginalised OCFs for the above OCF κ'_{abc} and Table 7.4 presents the discussed naive approach with each $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma_{abc})$ being accompanied by partitions \mathcal{P}_j with $j \in \{1, \dots, 4\}$ which correspond to the subset-sum solutions of $\omega \in \Omega(\Sigma_{abc})$.

Tab. 7.3.: Marginalised OCFs of κ'_{abc}

ω^1	κ_1	ω^6	κ_6	ω^2	κ_2	ω^5	κ_5	ω^3	κ_3	ω^4	κ_4
a	1	bc	3	b	1	ac	3	c	2	ab	1
\bar{a}	0	$b\bar{c}$	1	\bar{b}	0	$a\bar{c}$	1	\bar{c}	0	$a\bar{b}$	3
		$\bar{b}c$	2			$\bar{a}c$	2			$\bar{a}b$	3
		$\bar{b}\bar{c}$	0			$\bar{a}\bar{c}$	0			$\bar{a}\bar{b}$	0

Tab. 7.4.: Naive approach towards automated OCF-splitting

ω	κ	Subset-sum solutions	Partitions
abc	3	$= \kappa(ab) \oplus \kappa(c)$	\mathcal{P}_1
$ab\bar{c}$	1	$= \kappa(a) + \kappa(b\bar{c}) \vee \kappa(ab) \oplus \kappa(\bar{c})$	$\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_3$
$a\bar{b}c$	5	$= \kappa(a\bar{b}) \oplus \kappa(c)$	\mathcal{P}_1
$a\bar{b}\bar{c}$	3	$= \kappa(a\bar{b}) \oplus \kappa(\bar{c})$	\mathcal{P}_1
$\bar{a}bc$	5	$= \kappa(\bar{a}b) \oplus \kappa(c)$	\mathcal{P}_1
$\bar{a}b\bar{c}$	3	$= \kappa(\bar{a}b) \oplus \kappa(\bar{c})$	\mathcal{P}_1
$\bar{a}\bar{b}c$	2	$= \kappa(\bar{a}) + \kappa(\bar{b}c) \vee \kappa(\bar{b}) + \kappa(\bar{a}c) \vee \kappa(\bar{a}\bar{b}) \oplus \kappa(c) \vee \kappa(\bar{a}) + \kappa(\bar{b}) + \kappa(c)$	$\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4$
$\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c}$	0	$= \kappa(\bar{a}) + \kappa(\bar{b}\bar{c}) \vee \kappa(\bar{b}) + \kappa(\bar{a}\bar{c}) \vee \kappa(\bar{a}\bar{b}) \oplus \kappa(\bar{c}) \vee \kappa(\bar{a}) + \kappa(\bar{b}) + \kappa(\bar{c})$	$\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4$

What is striking here is that the addition for the partition \mathcal{P}_1 and hence the supposed splitting $\{a, b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$ is present in every row in Table 7.4, so it applies to every interpretation. As the subset-sum solutions correspond to specific partitions \mathcal{P}_j with $j \in \{1, \dots, 4\}$, forming the intersection from all those partitions yields the OCF-splittings for κ' , precisely $\{\mathcal{P}_1\} \cap \{\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_3\} \cap \{\mathcal{P}_1\} \cap \{\mathcal{P}_1\} \cap \{\mathcal{P}_1\} \cap \{\mathcal{P}_1\} \cap \{\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4\} \cap \{\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4\} = \mathcal{P}_1 = \{a, b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$. Furthermore, if one world does not have a subset-sum solution (*e.g.*, $\omega = \bar{a}\bar{b}c$ for κ in Table 7.1), the calculation can stop, since the intersection will then be the empty set, whether there are subset-sum solutions for other worlds or not. This process can be thought of as skeptical inferring the syntax splittings for an OCF.

That said, as OCFs—by their inherent arithmetic quality—do have unique finest splittings, the above approach could even be specified in so far as the finest partition is examined first to see if it is a splitting or not. In the above example, this would be the partition $\{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}\}$, but as can be seen, there are no κ_i with $\kappa = \kappa_1 \oplus \kappa_2 \oplus \kappa_3$ for all worlds, so the next finest partitions must be selected. Moreover, assuming the world $\omega = abc$ in Table 7.2, the only subset-sum solution is the partition $\{\{a, b\}, \{c\}\}$, which enormously limits the partitions to be checked.

A corresponding algorithm could probably be built on this observation, but the development of such an algorithm is beyond the scope of this work.

Another issue that has recently come to light is the idea of model transformations [HB22b], whereby a TPO or an OCF that has no splittings results in having splittings after an appropriate model transformation. The other direction is also possible, so that a plausibility order has splittings, but after a model transformation it no longer does.

The idea behind this is to take different perspectives when looking at situations that are to be modelled with an epistemic state. An implementation of functionalities to perform such model transformations would be an interesting extension for `InfOCF-Lib` to calculate whether, for example, a given TPO or OCF that has no splittings has splittings after a model transformation.

Although performing a syntax splitting on conditional knowledge bases is already very fast with the given implementation, there could be a considerable performance boost if the corresponding conditional knowledge base is transformed into an *antecedence normal form* [BK19] before computing its unique finest splitting. Here, the number of conditionals of a knowledge base is reduced according to a clear use of transformation rules, which would result in fewer computations in the initialisation of the set $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ in the context of the \mathcal{R} -splitting implemented in this work. However, the process of transformation itself would take some time, requiring first to check whether this approach really provides a performance advantage. Given that the initialisation of $\text{appl}(\mathcal{R})$ for $|\Sigma| = 56$ and $|\mathcal{R}| = 320$ takes about 4% of the total computation time, it can be assumed that this approach does not yield the desired performance increase at least for similarly large knowledge bases.

General Extensions of `InfOCF-Lib`

In addition to the possible extensions of `InfOCF-Lib` already mentioned, there are other conceivable ways to make working with `InfOCF-Lib` faster or more comfortable.

For example, the library could be parallelised in some computationally intensive places, which could increase the speed of the entire library. The executor service provided in this work can be used conveniently for this purpose and ensures that the code remains easily readable and maintainable.

In addition, with `InfOCF-Web`¹⁹ [KB21] there is also a provided web interface that can be equipped with the functionalities for `InfOCF-Lib` extended in this work.

¹⁹<https://www.fernuni-hagen.de/wbs/research/infocf-web/index.html#main>

For representation and layer mapping, the module `logic-components`²⁰ [Hel21] by Philip Heltweg could be used, as already done by Sauerwald and Heltweg in [SH21].

Relationship Between Splittings of Different Frameworks

An interesting research approach could be to look at the interrelationship of splittings in different frameworks. Kern-Isberner and Brewka have already established with Proposition 7.1 that every OCF-splitting is a TPO-splitting of the induced TPO as well as every TPO-splitting being also a \mathcal{T} -splitting [KIB17]. However, the reverse direction does not necessarily hold since the corresponding unique finest \mathcal{T} -splitting $\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$, derived from Example 7.1, does not imply the (coarser) TPO-splitting $\{a, b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}$ which in turn does not imply an OCF-splitting. For more information about the relationship between TPOs and OCFs and their property of having syntax splittings, see [HBKI21a; HB22b].

In Chapter 3 the observation was noted with Conjecture 3.1 that TPO-splittings do in fact have unique finest syntax splittings, yet not in the sense Parikh formulated them originally. Proving this property to be true could lead to new approaches and even better algorithms than provided here and although a formal proof is not provided by this thesis, empiric data with various different settings and layer mappings indicates that Conjecture 3.1 holds.

Overall, splittings in different frameworks do seem to depend on each other, so that syntax dependency in conditional knowledge bases manifests itself in TPO-splittings. On the other hand, there are cases where the associated \mathcal{T} -splitting breaks these dependencies and reveals a much more liberal syntax splitting, as Example 7.3 shows.

Example 7.3. Consider Example 2.5 with the signature $\Sigma_{birds} = \{p, b, f\}$, the conditional knowledge base $\mathcal{R}_{birds} = \{(f|b), (b|p), (\bar{f}|p)\}$, and the TPO \preceq_{birds} : $\bar{p}bf, \bar{p}\bar{b}f, \bar{p}\bar{b}\bar{f} \prec_{birds} pb\bar{f}, \bar{p}b\bar{f} \prec_{birds} pb\bar{f}, p\bar{b}\bar{f} \prec_{birds} p\bar{b}f$. The syntax of this particular conditional knowledge base cannot be split and the accompanying TPO \preceq_{birds} accepting this knowledge base has no splitting either. However, the belief set that can be excerpted from this TPO $\mathcal{T}_{birds} = \text{Cn}(\{\bar{p} \wedge (\bar{b} \vee f)\})$ does have a syntax splitting, *i.e.*, the unique finest \mathcal{T}_{birds} -splitting is $\{p\} \dot{\cup} \{b, f\}$.

As the TPO \preceq_{birds} from Example 7.3 does not even have a TPO-splitting, it agrees more with the non-existence of a splitting for the underlying knowledge base \mathcal{R}_{birds} .

²⁰<https://github.com/rhazn/logic-components>

Conclusion

The previous chapters have given insight into how the subject of relevance can be considered in the research area of symbolic artificial intelligence by means of syntax splitting. To this end, Chapter 1 first gave an impression of why it is necessary to distinguish between relevant and irrelevant knowledge in knowledge reasoning and also a brief insight into which approaches have been pursued so far.

Chapter 2 provided an overview of the basic foundations of classical propositional logic extended by TPOs and conditional knowledge bases, while Chapter 3 dealt with syntax splitting in the three frameworks of belief sets, epistemic states represented by TPOs and conditional knowledge bases.

Finally, in Chapter 4 algorithms were presented with which an automatic calculation of syntax splittings for TPOs and conditional knowledge bases can be realised. The implementation of these algorithms in the existing system `InfOCF-Lib` as well as the extension of `InfOCF-Lib` by TPOs was documented in Chapter 5.

To develop the algorithms, it was first necessary to extend the definitions provided in [KIB17] regarding TPO-splitting and [BHK121] regarding \mathcal{R} -splitting. Here, on the one hand, the notion of splittability was introduced, with which it became possible to solve TPO-splittings in the context of an extended knapsack problem. And secondly, the notion of epistemic relevance [Mak07] was translated to conditional knowledge bases, so that the notion of a unique finest \mathcal{T} -splitting can also be applied to conditional knowledge bases.

Enabling `InfOCF-Lib` to calculate TPO-splittings required first the capability to read and represent TPOs. With the help of this extension, it became possible to perform the calculation of TPO-splittings within `InfOCF-Lib`. For the computation of the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting, a corresponding functionality could be implemented directly, building on the already existing classes on conditional knowledge bases. In order to keep the exorbitant increasing runtime complexity of TPO-splittings within limits, an executor service was implemented in addition to the functionalities regarding syntax splitting and TPOs, with which a further parallelisation of `InfOCF-Lib` is comfortably possible.

The evaluation of the implemented algorithms in Chapter 6 presented a few key figures on which the complexity of the calculation of TPO-splittings depends and how it increases with additional signature elements. Furthermore, it was shown for the calculation of the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting that its calculation should generally be feasible with arbitrarily large knowledge bases, since no exponential growth is to be expected here. Parallelisation brings advantages for the calculation of all TPO-splittings in any case, but this does not necessarily apply to the calculation of the unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting.

Possible extensions and improvements for `InfOCF-Lib` as well as further research possibilities were discussed in Chapter 7, which additionally presents a basic approach of how to compute syntax splittings for OCFs. Besides the addressed possibilities, there might be plenty more space for improving `InfOCF-Lib`, and with each discovery made in the field of knowledge representation and reasoning the need for computational assistance grows. As such it is important to prioritise and take on implementations of the most relevant issues first.

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Appendices

Provided Files

Tab. A.1.: Provided software

File location	Note
Braeuer_2022.08.28.009.pdf	Master's Thesis PDF
latex_src/	Master's Thesis L ^A T _E X source files
InfOCF-Lib_SynSplit.jar	Artifact for conveniently calculating syntax splittings for conditional knowledge bases or total preorders from .cl files
synsplit.md	manual for usage of InfOCF-Lib_SynSplit.jar
InfOCF-Lib_V1.6/	Complete system InfOCF-Lib_V1.5 plus here listed additions
ChangeLog.md	Release note for version 1.6
examples/	
tpo_example0001.cl	Example file for reading TPOs
src/de/feruni_hagen/wbs/	
infocf_examples/	Example classes
TotalPreorderParser.java	
SyntaxSplittingExample.java	
ocf/	
RankingFunction.java	One additional method
text/parsing/	Additional files in parsing package
TpoParser.java	
SignatureParser.java	Extracted as abstract class from ConditionalKnowledgeBaseParser.java for more generic use
propositionalLogic/	
conditionalLogic/	
RSplitter.java	New class
ConditionalKnowledgeBase.java	Two additional methods
syntaxSplitting/	New package
Splittable.java	
SyntaxSplitter.java	
SyntaxSplittingFactory.java	
totalPreorder/	New package
Layer.java	
LayerMappingInconsistencyException.java	
TotalPreOrder.java	
Marginaliser.java	
TpoSyntaxSplitter.java	
util/	Additional files in util package
Executor.java	
SetOperations.java	
SubsetSumProblem.java	
Tuple.java	Integrated PowerSet.java

Additional Measurements

This chapter shows additional measurements that were taken during the evaluation.

Tab. B.1.: Factor of how an additional variable in Σ affects the runtime for sequential and concurrent processing.

$ \Sigma $	seq.	conc.
2 ↗ 3	9.54	7.67
3 ↗ 4	11.92	7.18
4 ↗ 5	14.14	13.55
5 ↗ 6	12.82	10.12
6 ↗ 7	12.92	12.56
7 ↗ 8	11.86	12.68

Tab. B.2.: Runtime of calculation for TPO-splitting with and without parallelisation overhead for different sizes of Σ . The measurements were taken in nanoseconds but are presented here in microseconds for brevity.

$ \Sigma $	Avg. speed sequential with overhead	Avg. speed sequential without overhead	Factor (with/without)
2	561.10 μs	493.03 μs	1.14
3	6,044.18 μs	4,705.03 μs	1.28
4	73,299.71 μs	56,088.84 μs	1.31
5	1,020,018.67 μs	792,821.37 μs	1.29
6	9,616,421.82 μs	10,161,737.98 μs	0.95
7	128,691,280.64 μs	131,317,970.19 μs	0.98
8	1,612,914,806.08 μs	1,561,621,082.80 μs	1.03

Tab. B.3.: Runtime of calculation for \mathcal{R} -splitting with and without parallelisation overhead. The measurements are presented in microseconds here.

$ \Sigma $ $ \mathcal{R} $	Avg. speed sequential with overhead	Avg. speed sequential without overhead	Factor (with/without)
7 4	87.52 μs	58.77 μs	1.49
7 5	87.61 μs	59.99 μs	1.46
7 6	81.57 μs	58.68 μs	1.39
7 7	101.41 μs	73.81 μs	1.37
7 8	111.45 μs	82.86 μs	1.35
14 11	96.76 μs	85.03 μs	1.14
14 12	155.42 μs	111.57 μs	1.39
14 13	120.30 μs	96.09 μs	1.25
14 14	128.05 μs	85.71 μs	1.49
14 15	236.54 μs	161.90 μs	1.46
14 16	115.73 μs	80.26 μs	1.44
14 17	227.90 μs	180.59 μs	1.26
14 18	198.20 μs	168.97 μs	1.17
14 19	251.52 μs	177.75 μs	1.42
14 20	244.38 μs	195.19 μs	1.25
56 20	15,816.98 μs	12,120.29 μs	1.31
56 40	45,648.89 μs	39,625.77 μs	1.15
56 80	286,923.82 μs	258,025.02 μs	1.11
56 160	159,113.44 μs	134,636.52 μs	1.18
56 240	288,157.61 μs	238,897.04 μs	1.21
56 320	259,015.28 μs	198,905.91 μs	1.30

Tab. B.4.: Runtime of calculation for \mathcal{R} -splitting sequential, parallelised, and parallelised with only two utilised cores. The measurements are presented in microseconds here.

	Processing	Avg. speed
$ \Sigma = 56, \mathcal{R} = 320$	sequential	198,905.91 μs
	4 cores	110,095.17 μs
	2 cores	52,177.81 μs

User Manual Extension

Throughout this thesis the term *formulae* has been used. However, since the existing user manual of `InfOCF-Lib` uses instead the term *formulas*, the following two sections will use the term *formulas* as well. This chapter is meant as an extension for the existing user manual provided by the documentation of `InfOCF-Lib`. It introduces functionalities for the representation of total preorders and to perform syntax splitting on total preorders as well as on conditional knowledge bases.

C.1 Total Preorders

This section introduces basic functionalities for generating total preorders on worlds and on formulas in `InfOCF-Lib` and provides Use-Cases accompanied by example code.

Providing a set of interpretations with a preferential ordering, a signature as usual is needed. Creating a total preorder over this signatures interpretations (worlds) is achieved by an array of integers accompanying them. The first integer provides the layer the world with truth assignments 0,0,0 would be in.

```

36 // Signature Sigma = {a,b,c}
37 PropositionalSignature signature =
38     new PropositionalSignature("a", "b", "c");
39 // Total preorder over the universe Omega(Sigma)
40 TotalPreOrder tpo =
41     new TotalPreOrder(signature, new int[]{
42         5, // layer index of interpretation 0,0,0
43         4, // layer index of interpretation 0,0,1
44         3, // layer index of interpretation 0,1,0
45         2, // layer index of interpretation 0,1,1
46         4, // layer index of interpretation 1,0,0
47         2, // layer index of interpretation 1,0,1
48         1, // layer index of interpretation 1,1,0
49         0 // layer index of interpretation 1,1,1
50     });
51
52 // Print tpo
53 System.out.println(tpo);

```

This will generate the output:

```
54 [1,1,1]<[1,1,0]<[0,1,1, 1,0,1]<[0,1,0]<[0,0,1, 1,0,0]<[0,0,0]
```

The total preorder completely corresponds to the given signature and its implications, as for example if the size of the given integer array does not match the size of interpretations for the present signature (*e.g.*, 7 assignments instead of expected 8), then a `LayerMappingInconsistencyException` is thrown:

```
55 Layer mapping has not the same size as your signatures
56 interpretations. Expected size of '8' got '7'.
```

Since OCFs induce total preorders, the method `getOcfInducedTpo` in the class `RankingFunction` returns the TPO induced by the defined OCF κ . With the above calculated set of OCFs `kappa` over the defined signature `signatureBirds` and the conditional knowledge base `kbBirds`, the lines

```
57 // Define OCF induced TPO
58 TotalPreOrder kappaInducedTPO =
59     kappa.getFirstRankingFunction().getOcfInducedTpo();
60
61 // Print OCF induced TPO
62 System.out.println(kappaInducedTPO);
```

return the following output:

```
63 [1,1,1, 1,0,0, 0,0,0]<[0,1,1, 1,0,1]<[0,0,1, 0,1,0]<[1,1,0]
```

Total preorders can be lifted to the level of formulas as well, where for a given signature and tpo mapping its total preorder of the corresponding complete conjunction can be called via the method `getTpoFormulasRepresentation`:

```
64 // String Representation of the total preorder over the set of
65 // complete conjunctions in Omega(Sigma)
66 var tpoForm =
67     tpo.getTpoFormulasRepresentation();
68
69 // Print tpoForm
70 System.out.println(tpoForm);
```

This will generate the output:

```

71 [(a,b,c)]<[(a,b,!c)]<[(a,!b,c), (!a,b,c)]<[(!a,b,!c)]<[(a,!b,!c),
72 (!a,!b,c)]<[(!a,!b,!c)]

```

Formulas can be compared preferentially, given an underlying total preorder, using the method `preferentialCompare` for an arbitrary number of formulas:

```

73 PropositionalAtom atomA =
74     new PropositionalAtom("a");
75 PropositionalAtom atomB =
76     new PropositionalAtom("b");
77
78 // Print preferential comparison of !ab, a!b and !a!b in the TPO
79 System.out.println(tpo.preferentialCompare(
80     atomA.neg().and(atomB)
81     ,atomA.and(atomB.neg())
82     ,atomA.neg().and(atomB.neg())
83     )
84     );

```

This will generate the following output:

```

85 [(!a,b),(a,!b)]<[(!a,!b)]

```

Marginalisation of total preorders is possible using the class `Marginaliser` with its method `generateMarginalisedStringRepresentation`, where

```

86 // marginalise tpoForm
87 var tpoMarg =
88     Marginaliser.generateMarginalisedStringRepresentation(tpo);
89
90 // Print tpoMarg
91 System.out.println(tpoMarg);

```

produces an output like this:

```

92 [[a] < [!a], [b] < [!b], [c] < [!c],
93 [(a,b)] < [(a,!b), (!a,b)] < [(!a,!b)],
94 [(a,c)] < [(a,!c)] < [(!a,c)] < [(!a,!c)],
95 [(b,c)] < [(b,!c)] < [(!b,c)] < [(!b,!c)]]

```

Analogous to the existing knowledge base parser in `InfOCF-Lib`, the class `TpoParser` offers methods for parsing signatures as usual and integer arrays needed for the construction of total preorders.

Conditional knowledge bases files (.cl-Files) can therefore start as usual with the keyword `signature` followed by a signature string. The keyword `tpo` starts the definition of the TPO, followed by the keyword `layermapping` and the comma-separated list of integers enclosed in curly-brackets.

```
signature
  a,b,c

tpo
layermapping{
5,4,3,2,4,2,1,0
}
```

C.2 Syntax Splitting

This section provides an overview of the classes and functionalities needed to perform syntax splitting for total preorders and conditional knowledge bases in `InfOCF-Lib` and gives Use-Cases with example code.

C.2.1 Syntax Splitting for TPOs

To perform syntax splitting [Par99] on different frameworks, a syntax splitting factory has been implemented.

A `splittingFactory` object and a syntax splitter of the type `TpoSyntaxSplitter` can be constructed with the following lines:

```
96 // Splitting factory for convenient use of syntax splitting
97 // functionalities
98 var splittingFactory =
99     new SyntaxSplittingFactory();
100
101 // Syntax splitter for the TotalPreOrder tpo
102 TpoSyntaxSplitter tpoSplitter =
103     splittingFactory.createSplitter(tpo);
```

The object `tpoSplitter` can now be used to calculate all TPO-splittings [KIB17] for the given TPO with the lines

```
104 // Print tpoSplitting
105 System.out.println(tpoSplitter.splitSyntax());
```

which produce the following output, where a space after a comma indicates the beginning of a new sub-signature:

```
106 [[a, c, b], [a, b,c]]
```

The splitting components are sub-signatures themselves and thus can be used as usual with the inherent functionalities of `InfoCF-Lib`.

Besides working with the actual class `TpoSyntaxSplitter`, the method `getSyntaxSplitting` can simply be called on a TPO, where the lines

```
107 // Print tpoSplitting
108 System.out.println(tpo.getSyntaxSplittings());
```

yield the same output as above.

Additionally the method `hasSplitting` can be called on a `TotalPreOrder` which returns true if the given partition is a TPO-splitting of the corresponding TPO. The lines

```
109 // Construct sub-signatures
110 PropositionalSignature subSig1 =
111     new PropositionalSignature("a");
112 PropositionalSignature subSig2 =
113     new PropositionalSignature("b", "c");
114
115 // Validate if the sub-signatures form a TPO-splitting
116 System.out.println(tpo.hasSplitting(subSig1, subSig2));
```

return true, since $\{\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b, c\}\} \in \{\{\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b, c\}\}, \{\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}\}\}$, while the lines

```
117 // Construct sub-signatures
118 PropositionalSignature subSig3 =
119     new PropositionalSignature("b");
120 PropositionalSignature subSig4 =
121     new PropositionalSignature("a", "c");
122
123 // Validate if the sub-signatures form a TPO-splitting
124 System.out.println(tpo.hasSplitting(subSig3, subSig4));
```

return false, since $\{\{b\} \dot{\cup} \{a, c\}\} \notin \{\{\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b, c\}\}, \{\{a\} \dot{\cup} \{b\} \dot{\cup} \{c\}\}\}$.

The method `getFinestSplitting` returns the finest syntax splitting for the corresponding TPO, where the lines

```
125 // Print finest tpoSplitting
126 System.out.println(tpo.getFinestSplitting());
```

simply produce the output

```
127 [a, c, b]
```

being the splitting with the most elements.

C.2.2 Syntax Splitting for conditional Knowledge Bases

Syntax splitting can also be performed on conditional knowledge bases [KIBB20; HB22a] using the `splittingFactory` as well. A conditional knowledge base is defined as usual.

```
128 // Defining signature signatureBirdEel
129 PropositionalSignature signatureBirdEel =
130     new PropositionalSignature("p", "b", "f", "e", "s");
131 PropositionalAtom penguin =
132     new PropositionalAtom("p");
133 PropositionalAtom bird =
134     new PropositionalAtom("b");
135 PropositionalAtom flying =
136     new PropositionalAtom("f");
137 PropositionalAtom eel =
138     new PropositionalAtom("e");
139 PropositionalAtom swimming =
140     new PropositionalAtom("s");
141
142 // Defining conditionals
143 Conditional penguinsAreBirds =
144     new Conditional(bird, penguin);
145 Conditional birdsFly =
146     new Conditional(flying, bird);
147 Conditional penguinsDontFly =
148     new Conditional(flying.neg(), penguin);
149 Conditional eelSwim =
150     new Conditional(swimming, eel);
151
152 // Defining conditional knowledge base kbBirdEel
153 ConditionalKnowledgeBase kbBirdEel =
154     new ConditionalKnowledgeBase(signatureBirdEel,
155     penguinsAreBirds,
156     birdsFly,
```

```

157         penguinsDontFly ,
158         eelSwim);

```

Using the conditional knowledge base as parameter, an `RSplitter` object can be constructed which can be used to split the syntax of the given conditional knowledge base and return its unique finest \mathcal{R} -splitting.

The lines

```

159 // Syntax splitter for the conditional knowledge base kbBirdEel
160 RSplitter kbSplitter =
161     splittingFactory.createSplitter(kbBirdEel);
162
163 // Print kbSplitting
164 System.out.println(kbSplitter.splitSyntax());

```

produce the following output:

```

165 [s,e, b,f,p]

```

The splitting components are sub-signatures themselves and thus can be used as usual with the inherent functionalities of `InfOCF-Lib`. Those sub-signatures can additionally be used as sub-signatures for the corresponding knowledge sub-base, *i.e.*, $\mathcal{R}_1 = \{(b|p), (f|b), (\bar{f}|p)\}$ and $\mathcal{R}_2 = \{(s|e)\}$.

The method `getSubKBs` constructs these knowledge sub-bases over their corresponding sub-signatures, where

```

166 // Printing the partitioned knowledge base kbBirdEel into subbases
167 // over split signatureBirdEel
168
169 System.out.println(kbSplitter.getSubKBs());

```

yields the following output:

```

170 [Knowledge Base Name: null
171 Signature: b,f,p
172 Conditionals:
173 ( f | b )
174 ( !f | p )
175 ( b | p )
176 , Knowledge Base Name: null
177 Signature: s,e
178 Conditionals:
179 ( s | e )
180 ]

```

Analogous to the syntax splitting on total preorders, performing syntax splittings on conditional knowledge bases can as well be performed without the direct usage of the splitting factory or the class `RSplitter`, where the lines

```
181 // Print kbSplitting
182
183 System.out.println(kbBirdEel.getSyntaxSplitting());
```

and the lines

```
184 // Printing the partitioned knowledge base kbBirdEel into subbases
185 // over split signatureBirdEel
186
187 System.out.println(kbBirdEel.getSplitKbs());
```

yield the same outputs as the lines above.

Colophon

This thesis was typeset with L^AT_EX. The layout of this thesis is initially based on the *Clean Thesis* style developed by Ricardo Langner and was extended in some areas. The design of the *Clean Thesis* style is inspired by user guide documents from Apple Inc.

The *Clean Thesis* style can be downloaded at <http://cleanthesis.der-ric.de/>.

